

Towards an Aggiornamento of Civil Liability: For the Recognition of Pure Animal Harm

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*“Our deepest luxury lies above all in the superb
ignorance of the thundering pain of animals
whose path we failed to cross.”*

*F. Burgat*¹

1. “A dog, to the galleys!”² It is not common to bring together the animal and procedure. The association readily evokes the historical trials of animals, or the fantasies of literature. Was it not Jean Racine who, in 1668, imagined the account of a dog brought before a judge in a celebrated three-act comedy? The play *Les Plaideurs* stages the comic situation of a judge, quite mad, surrounded by small puppies that “piss everywhere”,³ to decide the fate of a chicken-stealing bitch. In a few lines, the characters convey how the bringing of the animal before the court is a source of general confusion, not to say of ridicule. This is at least an imaginary that is easily cultivated, by allowing it to be believed that thinking together the animal and procedure constitutes a form of nonsense. Yet the issue of animal protection is emancipating itself from the comic register and, with it, from the procedural representation of the animal-as-wrongdoer, turning instead to the repair of harm inflicted upon the animal itself. The prism is thus more modern: it breaks with the most widespread symbol of the animal pointed at by proceedings and brings to light the animal-as-victim. This is accordingly an emerging subject, recently explored by Professor Fabien Marchadier in his article entitled “Le préjudice subi par l'animal”⁴. However, one must not be mistaken: the idea, rather recent among jurists, has long germinated in more creative minds. In 1655, in counterpoint to Racine's universe, Savinien Cyrano de Bergerac had described, in his *Histoire comique des États et Empires du Soleil*, the great trial of birds brought against Dyrcona, his human character accused of acting monstrously towards animals. While it is not our aim today to contend that animals could bring proceedings, pure animal harm deserves to attract serious attention. It consists of the harm suffered directly and exclusively by the animal. Can such harm give rise to compensation before the civil courts? To answer this question, it is necessary to move beyond the constant framework of animal protection, classically shaped by criminal law.

2. Beyond criminal law. The law centred on the protection of the animal embraces above all the field of criminal law, which has long been employed to repress conduct committed to the detriment of animals. From the Grammont Act to the recent loi no. 2021-1539 of 30 November 2021, animal protection has been conceived through the functions of criminal law, in a quasi-victimological approach — inasmuch as the animal has progressively been envisaged, since the Michelet Decree, as the principal object of protection, without, however, being associated with a victim status in the civil sense,⁵ which explains the importance of animal protection associations in this domain.

Does this mean, then, that civil law, and in particular the law of civil liability, remains numbed by a kind of torpor, indifferent to the fate of the animal-victim? It is true that the animal

¹F. Burgat, “Conclusion”, in F. Burgat (dir.), *Animal, mon prochain*, Odile Jacob, “Hors collection”, 1997, pp. 253–254.

²J. Racine, *Les Plaideurs*, Act III, scene 3.

³Ibid., Act III, scene 1.

⁴F. Marchadier, “Le préjudice subi par l'animal”, *Les Cahiers Portalis*, 2022/1 (no. 9), pp. 27–37.

⁵See *infra*, no. 22.

question is not the favoured subject of civil law; so much so that one might come to doubt whether this law is capable of offering solutions favourable to better animal protection, and whether, ultimately, such concerns genuinely fall within its functions.⁶ Yet civil liability constitutes a fertile terrain, insufficiently cultivated, which ought to complement the logic of the criminal arsenal by drawing all the consequences of civil fault causing harm to an animal. Why should such harm — even where it is, in certain cases, sufficiently serious to justify the engagement of criminal liability — have only limited scope in terms of the obligation to answer for its damaging consequences? And what of the other cases in which no criminal characterisation is warranted, yet suffering has been caused to the animal? The problem of civil reparation of pure animal harm must therefore be posed beyond criminal law. Addressing it requires determining the conditions of possibility of such harm, but also, beyond substantive law, identifying the holders of the liability action.

3. Beyond substantive law. In the debates it may provoke in France, the question of the aptitude of civil law to protect the animal is most often confined to arguments relating to the granting of legal personality to animals. While this perspective is stimulating, it can become an embarrassment when it monopolises judicial reasoning, making the recognition of properly animal harm exclusively dependent upon a theory of rights,⁷ itself contingent upon the legislature's goodwill. Now, neither the granting of legal personality nor the question of incapacity to hold patrimony constitutes the only argumentative framework available for conceiving such progress: procedural law, and in particular civil procedure, could possess sufficient potential to renew the application of civil liability rules at a lower cost — without recourse to rights, without recourse to patrimony. To demonstrate this, the inspiring relationship between substantive law and procedural law must first be brought to light.

Generally speaking, the relationship between substantive law and procedural law can give rise to radically divergent views. Viewed from substantive law, this relationship expresses the subordination of procedure to substance: the law of proceedings is a *law in service* articulated around the idea of the realisation and enforcement of substantive law.⁸ In this perspective, the recognition of a substantive right is primary, and it is only if such a right exists that proceedings, dedicated to its enforcement, are conceivable. This is the view that finds expression when it is held that the animal must have rights (and therefore legal personality) for its protection to be realised in justice.

The relationship is different if one observes matters from the standpoint of proceedings — and it is this perspective that proves promising. The primary condition, before the merits of the case are examined, is that the parties hold a right of action. The French Code of Civil Procedure, having adopted the ideas of Motulsky, apprehends the action as a *procedural subjective right*⁹ that is autonomous with respect to substantive law. A disconnection thus arises between the right of action and the substantive right. A right to bring proceedings may exist

⁶See, for instance: R. Libchaber, "La souffrance et les droits. À propos d'un statut de l'animal", *D.* 2014, 380, esp. no. 10: "If one wishes to engage with the Civil Code at all — accused of propagating a degrading image of the animal — one must do so bearing in mind its constraints and objectives. The Civil Code aims to organise the society of men by establishing bonds between them."

⁷See *infra*, nos. 17 and 21.

⁸G. Cornu and J. Foyer, *Procédure civile*, Thémis, PUF, 1996, pp. 6–7.

⁹H. Motulsky, *Principes d'une réalisation méthodique du droit privé. La théorie des éléments générateurs des droits subjectifs*, thesis pref. P. Roubier (dir.), 1948, Bibliothèque Dalloz, Dalloz, reissued 2002, pref. M.-A. Frison-Roche, esp. no. 31.

even though the litigant holds no substantive right (as is the case when the action is declared admissible but unfounded), and conversely, the action may be absent even though the litigant possesses a substantive right deserving protection.

Taken to its extreme, this procedural approach leads to placing substantive law in a position of dependence upon the right of action. Not only does the action condition the effectiveness of substantive rights, but it is also capable of assuming a degree of autonomy that renders substantive law superfluous. The recognition of an action may suffice to ensure the protection of certain “legal situations” (to adopt deliberately this term that Roubier used to designate legal prerogatives not erected into subjective rights¹⁰). These actions without substantive subjective rights, when admitted, nonetheless lead the judge to pronounce measures that will affect the legal order. What could be exploited is this *supplementary function* that procedure is capable of fulfilling in relation to substantive law: the aptitude of procedural rules to produce results that rules of substantive law do not permit, and which prove sufficient to ensure the correct functioning of the legal order.¹¹

So envisaged, the procedural prism opens useful avenues for animal law, which must *seize* procedure. The question, from this standpoint, is less whether the animal holds a right to reparation of its pure harm than whether there can exist a liability action capable of compensating that pure animal harm.

4. Towards a purely animal harm. If the animal suffers, it is because it has an interest in not suffering. It is therefore, at the very least, a moral patient. It is doubtless also a legal patient. Indeed, if laws organise the protection of the animal, the fight against its mistreatment, and the respect owed to it, it is precisely because its interest in not suffering is worthy of legal protection, without this implying a

shift towards a debate regarding the recognition of a “right not to suffer”,¹² which too often monopolises reasoning directed at the development of animal law and, as a result, unfortunately paralyses its improvement.¹³ In a utilitarian approach, this interest in not suffering already suffices to rehabilitate the ethical relationship between man and animal but

¹⁰P. Roubier, *Droits subjectifs et situations juridiques*, 1963, Dalloz, Philosophie du droit, p. 8.

¹¹As illustrated, for instance, by the cases in which a judge rules without having been seised of the principal claim — as in interlocutory proceedings, which adopt measures not founded on the application of private-law rules. See esp. N. Cayrol, *Procédure civile*, Cours Dalloz, 4th edn., 2022, nos. 493 et seq.

¹²See: R. Libchaber, “La souffrance et les droits. À propos d'un statut de l'animal”, *D.* 2014, 380, esp. no. 4: “one can readily conceive of the existence of a moral obligation not to cause animals needless suffering; but must one infer from this that they can invoke a ‘right not to suffer’ that can be accounted for in legal terms?”. This direct passage from morality to subjective right is symptomatic of the occlusion of the notion of interest — which has precisely the virtue of avoiding reasoning in terms of personality or rights. In this regard, while often invoked, utilitarian theory is not always exploited in accordance with its principles. Furthermore, even if since Ihering the subjective right is sometimes defined as a “legally protected interest” — which may give the impression that the legal protection of an interest amounts to recognising a right (see P.-J. Delage, *La condition animale. Essai juridique sur les justes places de l'Homme et de l'animal*, thesis Limoges, dactyl., J.-P. Marguénaud (dir.), 2013, no. 120) — the confusion between right and interest must be carefully set aside, as several authors, including Roubier, have endeavoured to demonstrate. The subjective right implies a heightened level of control, comprising “exclusivity” and “free disposal”; it carries far stronger “legal prerogatives”, a mere interest being primarily protected through the sanctioning of infringements upon it (see F. Ost, *Droit et intérêt, vol. 2: entre droit et non-droit: l'intérêt*, Publications des facultés universitaires Saint-Louis, Brussels, 1990, pp. 28 and 38). This distinction is all the more important in that it enables the field of theoretical possibilities and technical variations offered by utilitarian approaches to be exploited. Confining oneself to “all subjective rights” amounts to limiting both the normative choices of the legislature and those of the courts and litigants.

¹³See F. Chénéde, “La personnification de l'animal: un débat inutile?”, *AJ Famille* 2012, 72: “These are the questions that must not be obscured. There is no need to brandish the mask of legal personality for this!” Add: “Le droit civil, au naturel (ou l'actualité d'un passé)”, *RTD civ.* 2020, 506.

also, at the legal level, to envisage actions liberated from considerations relating to the categorisation of things and beings.

In fact, is not an interest worthy of protection also worthy of reparation when it is harmed? Why, then, should civil liability protect the interest of the owner whose animal-property has been harmed, without protecting the interest of the animal-victim? It is true that the general clause of liability provided for by the former Article 1382 of the Civil Code was doubtless conceived from an anthropocentric perspective. Must the same be true of the new Article 1240, which postdates loi no. 2015-177 of 16 February 2015 on modernisation and simplification? Does not a reading of the new Article 1240 in the light of its own time, within its new normative context, say something different about what may be understood by “another” (*autrui*)? In other words, does not the combination of Article 515-14 of the Civil Code and Article 1240 of the Civil Code, and the effects of the redrafting of the former Article 528 of the Civil Code, require civil protection of the animal-as-sentient-being when man causes it harm? Furthermore, at a time when pure ecological harm has been recognised by case law and enshrined by the legislature, is it not possible to envisage, on a comparable model, the reparation of purely animal harm? Environmental law scholars proclaim it: “the spirit of the Civil Code has changed”.¹⁴ It is therefore time that, with regard to the civil protection of the animal, the law of civil liability assumes its *aggiornamento*. The thesis advanced is accordingly that the contextually reread Article 1240 of the Civil Code — within its normative environment — ought to be capable of serving as a foundation for the admission of pure animal harm, without the legislature needing to create a hypothetical Article 1240-1 providing that harm caused to an animal must be repaired. Positive law already contains the material favourable to the reasoning leading to the possible recognition of pure animal harm, both at the theoretical and practical levels. The wager undertaken here is therefore the following: an ambitious end, an economy of means.¹⁵

To be convinced of this, it is necessary to revisit the current conditions of liability actions in cases of harm caused to an animal. Such actions are focused on interests diverted from the individual animal. They suffer as a result from a persistent inadequacy (I), whereas, in the light of the most recent reforms in civil liability, their adaptation is possible (II).

I. THE PERSISTENT INADEQUACY OF LIABILITY ACTIONS

5. Why such inhibition? At present, the liability action is apprehended solely from the angle of the reparation of harm *derived* from harm to the animal and not concerning the animal in the first place: the actions classically employed are limited (A). One must be astonished at these limitations, which appear to be sustained by a certain inhibition, particularly in judicial practice. It will be seen that, despite the legislative renewal in this field, the potential of civil liability is currently unexploited (B).

¹⁴G. Leray, J. Bardy, G.J. Martin and S. Vanuxem, “Réflexions sur une application jurisprudentielle du préjudice écologique”, *D.* 2020, 1553.

¹⁵See *infra*, no. 45: Annex — Summary table of the argument.

A. THE LIMITATIONS OF THE ACTIONS CLASSICALLY EMPLOYED

6. Indirect consideration. In the current state of judicial practice, harm suffered by the animal is taken into account in an indirect manner. Only the *derived* harm, personally sustained by legal persons, is repaired, which has led courts of first instance to set aside purely animal harm. This is what emerges from the successive examination of the two principal types of liability action before the civil courts: first, the action diverted to the benefit of the owner of the animal (1) and, second, the poorly calibrated action of animal protection associations (2).

1. The Action Diverted to the Benefit of the Owner

7. Defence of the owner's personal interest. If an animal sustains harm, its owner holds an action against the person who caused it. It is therefore the owner who benefits from the proceedings; it is the owner who seeks compensation by addressing the court; it is *his* interest that is at issue.¹⁶ The owner may claim the reparation of his own harm: both material and harm of affection.

8. Material harm. It is well established that, for the owner, the animal represents an element of his patrimony, that is to say a *property (bien)*. He will accordingly be able to claim reparation if he can demonstrate that his animal had an economic value or contributed to an economic activity that can no longer be pursued under the same conditions. This harm extends to the loss of goods produced by the harmed animal.¹⁷ Furthermore, all expenses incurred in order to treat the injuries suffered by the animal constitute recoverable expenditure. This is the case for veterinary fees.¹⁸

9. Harm of affection. The owner may also claim reparation for non-pecuniary harm when he has developed an affective bond with his animal. The celebrated *Lunus* judgment handed down by the Cour de cassation in 1962¹⁹ admitted compensation for the affective harm suffered by a rider by reason of his horse's death following electrocution. In that case, what is repaired is not the animal's suffering but the infringement of the rider's feelings²⁰ by reason of the animal's suffering or death. Furthermore, even in the absence of the animal's death, case law attests to the recoverability of the "non-pecuniary harm linked to the painful experience of injuries inflicted on [the] animal".²¹

¹⁶CA Nîmes, ch. civ. 2A, 27 Oct. 2011, no. 10/03389, *RSDA* 2011/2, p. 35, obs. F. Marchadier.

¹⁷It is thus that compensation is granted for the loss of eggs following the death of hens killed by a dog (CA Limoges, ch. civ., 13 Apr. 2022, no. 21/00657).

¹⁸See, e.g., CA Angers, ch. a – civ., 8 Feb. 2022, no. 18/00654.

¹⁹Civ. 1re, 16 Jan. 1962, *D.* 1962, 199, note P. Rodière.

²⁰H. Gali, *Le préjudice moral. Étude de droit de la responsabilité civile*, thesis pref. L. Neyret (dir.), Nouvelle Bibliothèque des thèses, Dalloz, 2021, no. 79; J.-P. Marguénaud, "La protection juridique du lien d'affection envers un animal", *D.* 2004, 3009.

²¹CA Angers, ch. A – civ., 8 Feb. 2022, no. 18/00654.

The affective bond must nonetheless be established for this non-pecuniary harm to be repaired. In this regard, several questions arise that attest to the absence of automatic recognition of this head of harm.

— *First*, must a distinction be drawn according to the animal's purpose? There is little doubt that a pet has an affective value for its owner. It is in this perspective that a judgment of the Cour de cassation of 9 December 2015, the *Delgado* judgment, describes a dog as “a living being, unique and irreplaceable, destined to receive its owner's affection, with no economic vocation whatsoever”.²² From this it is deduced that the pet is non-fungible. Is the same true of an animal with an economic value? The reasoning expressed by the *tribunal d'instance* of Vannes, the terms of whose judgment are reproduced in the *Delgado* decision, invites doubt on this point. Indeed, the tribunal had found it necessary to compare the dog's situation to that of a dairy cow in the following terms: “destined to receive its owner's affection in return for its company and having no economic vocation, as a dairy cow does, it is all the more impossible to replace, being the receptacle of a unique affection”. This comparison could be interpreted as a manner of denying the possibility, for the owner, of combining compensation for both harm to the economic value and harm to the affective value of the animal. In other words, it might suggest that the recognition of the affective value of the pet is a sort of palliative for the absence of economic value to the owner, simply designed to allow compensation for the owner's harm. Such is not the case: the principle of full reparation requires that if both heads of harm are established, each must give rise to compensation. One may further ask whether the comparison drawn with the dairy cow does not amount to asserting a negation — namely, the denial of the affective value of a farm animal.²³ Such an exclusion would proceed from an assumption with no clearly identifiable legal basis. Why should the cattle farmer, to remain with the argumentative choice made by the Vannes judge, be unable to have recognised the affective bond he may have developed with his animals? The farmer who causes to be born, accompanies, and treats the animals whose welfare he must — in principle — guarantee, cannot he demonstrate that he attributes an affective value to his animal, and not solely an economic value²⁴; perhaps even an affectivity in the service of welfare? The question remains open. The fact is that the consideration given to the relationship with the animal is potentially “of variable geometry”, in a manner unfavourable to animals whose purpose is other than to “receive the affection of a master”.²⁵

²²Civ. 1re, 9 Dec. 2015, no. 14-25.910. The decision responded to the question of whether consumer law rules — providing that a professional seller, who is bound to repair a defective item, may propose its replacement when the cost of repair is excessive relative to the item's value — ought to apply. The court held that they should not: the value of a pet animal is an affective value.

²³A farm animal does not enjoy the same favourable presumption as a domestic animal. It is accordingly habitually subjected to physical and psychological constraints from which domestic animals are exempt. Professor Fabien Marchadier rightly observes that: “harm to the physical integrity of animals [especially farm animals], restrictions on their freedom of movement and on the expression of their natural behaviours, do not normally call for criminal or civil condemnation. Certainly, this immeasurable quantity of violence inflicted on animals does not leave everyone indifferent. The primary concern is to limit or avoid it by developing welfare norms”: in “Le préjudice subi par l'animal”, *op. cit.* On the occlusion of the farm animal and its treatment, see E. Baratay, *Bêtes de somme. Des animaux au service des hommes*, Points, Histoire, 2008, esp. p. 109 et seq.; F. Burgat, *Les animaux d'élevage ont-ils droit au bien-être?*, INRA Editions, 2001; X. Perrot, “La construction de l'animal technico-économique. Genèse et faillite programmée du système d'élevage industriel”, *RSDA*, 2014/2, pp. 287–310. Add, for a general overview of the development of zootechnics: R. Jussiau *et al.*, *L'élevage en France. 10000 ans d'histoire*, Educagri, 2000.

²⁴On the question of the emotional bond between the farmer and the animal, and more fundamentally on what should be understood by “affectivity”, see esp. J. Porcher, “Chapitre 3. De l'amitié avant toute chose”, in J. Porcher (dir.), *Éleveurs et animaux: réinventer le lien*, PUF, “Partage du savoir”, 2002, pp. 91–150.

²⁵J. Porcher, art. cit., no. 13. It is noted that “the relationship between humans and animals, particularly in relations with the family pet, (...) retains a blurred and ambiguous character, as if there were something improper about delving into this subject”. Mme Porcher further adds that “the relationship between humans and animals, particularly in relations with the family pet,

— *Second*, since the affective bond is not presumed, even in relation to a domestic animal, the question of proof of the reality of this affection for the animal arises. This is a question of fact giving rise to an *in concreto* assessment. Thus, one judgment of the Lyon Court of Appeal affirms the owner's subjective and affective harm by reason of the affective bond, proved by several testimonies, between the owner and his dog violently killed by another dog.²⁶ In contrast, in another case, the owner is dismissed because the affective bond with the animal was characterised with her minor daughter, who was not a party to the proceedings.²⁷ In one first-instance decision, the judge takes into consideration the argument that the owner had appeared indifferent to the fate of the animal (concluding, in the case at hand, that this was not so).²⁸

It follows from these elements nonetheless that civil liability does not take into account animal sentience, which “has little bearing on the protection owed to animals, save for an increase in the protection of the animal's owner, who will be able to claim damages for the non-pecuniary loss suffered following the disappearance or injury of his animal”.²⁹

10. Rejection of pure animal harm. Whether it is material harm or non-pecuniary harm, the owner claims, as can be seen, solely the reparation of harm connected to the suffering he has personally sustained. Should he attempt to rely upon harm arising from injury to the animal's physical or psychological integrity — in other words, pure animal harm, characterised by the suffering experienced by the animal as an individual — his claims will be rejected by the courts. Thus, the Lyon Court of Appeal, in a judgment of 20 April 2009, holds that the owner “did not personally sustain any harm to physical integrity; this was experienced by his dog and he is therefore not entitled to claim its reparation”.³⁰ Particularly illustrative of this position is the so-called *Saphir horse* case.³¹ The court rejected the claim for reparation of purely animal harm on the grounds that “the protection owed to the animal and to its natural habitat cannot, however, lead to recognising any legal personality in the animal or to making it a 'subject' of civil rights” (where the obstacle-argument of the absence of legal personality

retains a blurred and not unambiguous character, as if there were something improper about delving into this subject”. One may ask whether the utilitarian function of the animal, and its designated purpose, are the exclusive indicators of the bond likely to develop between the farmer and his animal — one may also suspect that the proper realisation (both ethical and pragmatic) of the utilitarian relationship implies the development of an affective bond.

²⁶CA Lyon, 6e ch., 6 Dec. 2018, no. 17/05889: “Whereas the death of dog X, a living being endowed with sentience within the meaning of Article 515-14 of the Civil Code, occurring under dramatically brutal circumstances [bite by another dog placed under its owner's guardianship], constitutes for Mrs B Y a subjective and affective harm giving rise to compensation, the bond of affection linking her to that animal being attested by numerous testimonies; that this head of harm shall be justly compensated by the allocation of a sum of 3,000 euros to be borne by Mrs D Z. That Mrs B Y is also entitled to obtain compensation for her material harm in the amount claimed of 1,170 euros, which is found to be justified (purchase value of the animal, post-mortem care costs and cremation costs).”

²⁷CA Lyon, 1re ch. civ. a, 8 Nov. 2018, no. 17/01664: “The court of first instance rightly held that the witness statements recounting the particular grief felt by Rebecca, the daughter of Mrs D G, do not establish a specific harm of affection suffered by the latter, who acts in the present proceedings in her personal name and not on behalf of her minor daughter; no specific harm of affection is therefore to be taken into account in her respect, and the judgment, which fixed at the just sum of 500 euros the compensation for the harm of each of the parties concerned, deserves confirmation.”

²⁸Trib. prox. Saint-Germain en Laye, 5 July 2022, no. 11-22-292.

²⁹M. Lacroix and G. Gidrol-Mistral, “L'animal: un nouveau centaure dans les curies de la responsabilité civile?”, *Revue du notariat*, 120(2). The analysis is conducted in the light of the Quebec Civil Code, but can readily be transposed to French law.

³⁰CA Lyon, 20 Apr. 2009, no. 08/01427.

³¹J.-P. Marguénaud, “Le cheval Saphir à la croisée des pistes juridiques”, *RSDA*, 2018/1, p. 15.

stands out clearly). Other recent decisions rely upon this decisive ground that animals “are not legal subjects”.³²

Before engaging in the deconstruction of this reasoning — whose validity is not established — it should be recalled that the owner is not alone in being able to bring a liability action: associations may equally do so, but their action is not well calibrated.

2. The Poorly Calibrated Action of Associations

11. Actions in defence of a collective interest. Since a judgment handed down on 18 September 2008, the Cour de cassation has enshrined the principle that “even in the absence of legislative authorisation, and in the absence of an express statutory provision regarding the use of judicial channels, an association may bring proceedings in the name of collective interests provided that those interests fall within its objects”.³³ This notion of “collective interests falling within the association's objects” is not easy to define. It consists, according to the persuasive analysis of certain authors, of a “functional notion” covering the defence of a “social category”³⁴ or a “cause”,³⁵ a cause that may be more or less abstract and need not cover the interests of legal persons. Accordingly, associations whose objects include the defence of animals may assuredly bring proceedings for the defence of that collective interest. Does this mean that such an action brought in the collective interest would permit the reparation of pure animal harm to be claimed?

Two theoretical obstacles appear to stand in the way. They concern both the possibility of obtaining reparation under the head of defending a collective interest, and the possibility of including the interest of the individual animal within the collective interest.

— *First*, harm to the collective interest opens a right of action for the association — but does it, from a substantive standpoint, found a right to reparation in favour of the group? For this to be so, harm to the collective interest would need to give rise to recoverable damage, which encounters serious objections.

One might envisage the existence of non-pecuniary harm. Case law inclines in this direction. Thus, the Cour de cassation recognises “indirect non-pecuniary harm” of associations by reason of harm to collective interests.³⁶ In the domain of animal law, one may also note a decision of the Rouen Court of Appeal compensating the harm “on all grounds” of an

³²CA Saint-Denis de la Réunion, civil division, 1 Apr. 2022, no. 21/00151; CA Grenoble, 1re ch., 12 Apr. 2022, no. 20/00795: “no indemnity may be awarded to Mrs Z in respect of the animal's suffering, which is, admittedly, a living being endowed with sentience, but is not a legal subject.”

³³Civ. 1re, 18 Sept. 2008, no. 06-22.038, Bull. civ. I, no. 201.

³⁴L. Cadiet and E. Jeuland, *Droit judiciaire privé*, LexisNexis, 11th edn., 2020, no. 361.

³⁵J. Héron, Th. Le Bars and K. Salhi, *Droit judiciaire privé*, 7th edn., LGDJ, Domat droit privé, 2019, no. 78. On the reference to “great causes”: C. Chainais, F. Ferrand, L. Mayer and S. Guinchard, *Procédure civile*, Précis Dalloz, 36th edn., 2022, no. 326; v° “Action en justice — Intérêt direct et personnel”, *Rép. proc. civ.*, N. Cayrol, Dalloz, 2019 [updated: Oct. 2022], no. 498; M. Douchy-Oudot, *Procédure civile*, Gualino – Lextenso, 6th edn., 2014, no. 151. Add L. Boré, *La défense des intérêts collectifs par les associations devant les juridictions administratives et judiciaires*, thesis pref. G. Viney (dir.), LGDJ, 1997.

³⁶Civ. 3e, 9 June 2010, no. 09-11.738; Civ. 3e, 8 June 2011, no. 10-15.500. Add: CA Pau, 1re ch., 14 Dec. 2021, no. 20/00175: “This infringement alone suffices to establish its indirect moral harm.” See M. Bandrac, “Vérification de la qualité à agir”, in S. Guinchard (dir.), *Droit et pratique de la procédure civile*, Dalloz Action, 10th edn., 2021, no. 212.323.

association, within which falls “harm to collective interests”.³⁷ It remains the case that, at the theoretical level, the existence of non-pecuniary harm is open to question. As certain authors explain, there is in this recognition a “characteristic anthropomorphism”³⁸ since the association has no feelings or moral conscience that could be harmed. The harm is artificially attached to the person of the association.³⁹

Alternatively, one might consider the existence of autonomous harm caused to the collective interest.⁴⁰ Certain authors admit the notion of “collective harm” as covering “direct or indirect harm to the collective interest”⁴¹ or envisage that harm to the collective interest gives rise to “objective” harm.⁴² These doctrinal proposals are meaningful, but they do not escape criticism. If one admits that the collective interest is a “cause”, then “a cause (...) feels nothing and has no patrimony”,⁴³ so that it does not, strictly speaking, sustain harm. The problem then lies in the abstraction underlying the notion of collective interest, an abstraction that impedes the taking into account of harm suffered by the individual animal. In reality, from a logical standpoint, actions in defence of the collective interest ought only to be capable of seeking a declaration of illegality, the obtaining of cessation measures, or, where appropriate, the compensation of material harm.⁴⁴

— *Second*, the interest of the individual animal is individual, which is the counterpoint of the idea of collectivity, which implies at least a plurality of interests. The collective interest springs from a collection of individual interests. Consequently, the collective interest is an abstraction. While it may allow the suffering inflicted on a particular animal to be seized, it does so insofar as that animal embodies the fate of the collectivity of animals. It is not the animal's own and individual interest that is defended, but the interest of animals insofar as it is actualised in a situation concerning a particular individual animal. From a theoretical standpoint, this distinction is fundamental. It is upon this distinction that animal law builds itself by emancipating itself from environmental law. Environmental law, like the collective interest, apprehends the animal as part of a larger whole that is nature, and treats it therein often at the level of its species. This is insufficient to repair harm caused to a particular animal. Indeed, there exists a relative natural indifference of environmental law towards pets or farm animals, which do not constitute its primary frame of reference. Thus, the broadly biocentric approach of environmental law takes into account interests that may be different, or even divergent, when compared to that of the individual animal. Animal law is in this sense

³⁷CA Rouen, ch. corr., 16 Sept. 2009, no. 08/01085: “As regards the harm, the Société Normande de Protection des Animaux establishes only the actual payment of veterinary care costs for vaccinations, amounting to 1,030 euros. Payment of transport and boarding costs for the ponies amounting to 9,389.75 euros up to July 2008 — at which time the ponies would have been entrusted to members of the association in order to limit accommodation costs — is not established, only one invoice being produced without proof of payment. It is, however, an established fact that the Société Normande de Protection des Animaux actively contributed to the rescue of the ponies by agreeing, in particular, to implement their placement on 25 April 2008 at the request of the Rouen veterinary services directorate, and that the acts prosecuted infringed upon the collective interests which it has taken as its mission to defend. In this state, on all grounds, the harm suffered by the Société Normande de Protection des Animaux shall be compensated by the sum of 3,000 euros.”

³⁸J. Héron, Th. Le Bars and K. Salhi, *Droit judiciaire privé*, LGDJ, Domat droit privé, 7th edn., 2019, no. 82.

³⁹O. Sabard, “Le préjudice moral”, in *Hommage en l'honneur de Grégoire Forest*, 2014, Dalloz, Thèmes et commentaires, pp. 247–260, esp. p. 252.

⁴⁰J. Héron, Th. Le Bars and K. Salhi, *Droit judiciaire privé*, LGDJ, Domat droit privé, 7th edn., 2019, no. 82.

⁴¹Ph. Malinvaud, M. Mekki and J.-B. Seube, *Droit des obligations*, LexisNexis, 15th edn., 2019, no. 639.

⁴²H. Gali, *op. cit.*, no. 419.

⁴³J. Héron, Th. Le Bars and K. Salhi, *Droit judiciaire privé*, LGDJ, Domat droit privé, 7th edn., 2019, no. 82.

⁴⁴Ibid.

zoocentred — that is, focused on the treatment of animals considered independently of ecological concerns — which does not preclude certain issues from being intertwined.

12. Actions for reparation of pure ecological harm. Beyond the general framework of actions in defence of the collective interest, it should be recalled that loi no. 2016-1087 of 8 August 2016 for the reconquest of biodiversity, nature, and landscapes introduced into civil law the possibility of repairing pure ecological harm.⁴⁵ The action is open to several categories of persons, including “approved associations or those created at least five years before the date of the introduction of proceedings whose object is the protection of nature and the defence of the environment”.⁴⁶ The recognition of this action constitutes an advance for the compensation of harm suffered by animals, but it remains insufficient.⁴⁷ Indeed, the actions of associations for reparation of ecological harm may have the consequence of repairing harm suffered by animals. The suffering undergone by animals may be apprehended as an element in the evaluation of pure ecological harm within the meaning of Articles 1246 and following of the Civil Code. Under Article 1249 of the Civil Code, “the reparation of ecological harm is effected by preference in kind”. Measures of reparation in kind may therefore be directed at improving the situation of populations of animals that suffer.

The outcome may prove satisfactory from a pragmatic standpoint. It remains the case nonetheless that the object of such an action is not focused on the animal individual's own interest, running up against the same limit as the action in defence of the collective interests of animals (and resting, moreover, on a threshold of activation far more monumental than the mere harm caused to an individual animal).

13. Assessment. Two lessons emerge from the foregoing.

The first lesson is that judicial practice tends to deny the possibility of directly claiming compensation for purely animal harm. The courts are in principle reluctant to repair harm not sustained by a legal person. Yet this judicial practice must not be systematised. It rests on fragile foundations: on the one hand, because the Cour de cassation has never had occasion to rule on the question; on the other hand, because it results from isolated decisions that are insufficient to constitute settled case law. The matter is therefore not closed.

The second lesson is that consideration of such suffering may appear indirectly and constitute fertile ground for an evolution. This is so in the context of the reparation of the owner's harm of affection, in the recognition — extensive and even technically debatable — of an “indirect non-pecuniary harm” of associations, or in the modalities for evaluating pure ecological harm. The exploitation of these legal techniques attaches animal suffering — which is not contested — to harm sustained by a legal person.

⁴⁵Arts. 1246 *et seq.*, Civil Code. See G. Leray, J. Bardy, G.J. Martin, S. Vanuxem, “Réflexions sur une application jurisprudentielle du préjudice écologique”, *D.* 2020, 1553.

⁴⁶Art. 1248, Civil Code.

⁴⁷See in particular A. Mure, *L'évolution du préjudice de la victime en droit de la responsabilité civile*, thesis Grenoble Alpes, 2019, esp. p. 9: “In the absence of a direct victim, it becomes impossible to repair harm caused directly to Nature — independently of its repercussions on humans — whereas its frequency and magnitude are growing. The legislature, in 2008, acknowledged this need to act by transposing a directive on environmental liability. This environmental liability is, however, of a hybrid character, since, in order to be effective, it requires the full versatility of the law, not only public but also private. In this perspective, it is civil liability that has appeared most capable of complementing it to reinforce its effectiveness.” Add pp. 57, 74 *et seq.*

The current state of these actions is accordingly unsatisfactory. While the indirect consideration of animal suffering by the aforementioned actions may occasionally lead to acceptable results, their deployment for this purpose remains ill-adapted and always uncertain: this does not guarantee efficient protection of the animal by civil liability.

This is why the fundamental assumption must be called into question — namely, that which consists principally of making the animal's legal status the alpha and omega of its civil protection. This assumption can, however, be overcome in the context of the renewal of substantive stakes since 2015.

B. THE CURRENTLY UNEXPLOITED POTENTIAL OF CIVIL LIABILITY

14. Rereading the law of civil liability. At the substantive level, the law of civil liability proves sufficiently receptive to admit actions founded on the animal's own interest. The opportunity to exploit this branch of law (1) coincides with the possibility — both philosophical and technical — of lodging within it the compensation of pure animal harm (2).

1. The Opportunity to Exploit Civil Liability

15. Abandoning the tropism towards criminal law. Substantive law in favour of the protection of the animal has historically been constructed by placing upon human beings duties towards animals and by repressing certain unjustified harm inflicted upon them. It is therefore criminal law that has laid the foundations of animal protection, for various reasons, sometimes antagonistic, and through various developments. Suffice it to note that the liability of the authors of harm caused to animals has been built upon a logic of sanction-repression rather than sanction-reparation. There exists, in this regard, a kind of tropism towards criminal law in animal protection that must not obscure the role that civil liability is called upon to play. This tropism is particularly evident in the decision handed down by the former *tribunal de grande instance* of Metz regarding the horse Saphir.⁴⁸ The refusal of the owner's claims is notably grounded on the reason that “the suffering undergone by the animal as a result of the failure to treat its acute laminitis could clearly not be analysed as voluntary acts of cruelty or abuse, which are as such repressed by the Criminal Code”. The reasoning expressed clearly conveys the assumption that only the criminal judge is capable of sanctioning harm caused to an animal. Yet this view is open to criticism. The argument is reductive and inoperative: it strangely makes civil fault dependent upon criminal fault. The practical stakes are considerable since, as Professor Jean-Pierre Marguénaud writes, the choice made by the court demonstrates that “in the current state of French law, there are a multitude of situations in which, for want of being able to apply criminal law by reason of the principle of legality of the criminal law, nothing can legally be done for the animal whose welfare has not been concretely respected or safeguarded”.⁴⁹ This says a great deal about how civil liability has been divested of the question of the treatment of the animal. This inhibition no longer has any justification. Beyond its

48J.-P. Marguénaud, "Le cheval Saphir à la croisée des pistes juridiques", *RSDA*, 2018/1, p. 15.

49J.-P. Marguénaud, "Le cheval Saphir à la croisée des pistes juridiques", *op. cit.*, p. 18.

corrective function, its normative function is precious: civil sanctions contribute to public morality insofar as they influence socially desirable conduct.

16. Exploiting the normative function of civil liability. The consolidation of the normative function of civil liability requires compelling the responsible party not only to answer civilly for his conduct but also to compensate the harm suffered by the animal. Assuredly, this function has a preponderant role to play and cannot be satisfied by symbolic condemnations. Was it not Aulus Gellius who bore witness to this, in an anecdote classically invoked in the history of the law of obligations?⁵⁰ He recounted how a Roman knight, Lucius Veratius, taking advantage of the modest sum attached to the *injuria* (minor harm provided for by the Law of the Twelve Tables), took pleasure in slapping passers-by, followed by his slave who promptly distributed the few coins owed to the victims. The meagre amount of reparation literally allowed him to “afford” the harmful acts. If the anecdote lends itself to a profound reflection, within the grand History, on the functions of liability, it reminds us here that the minimisation of harm and its reparation is detrimental to the objectives pursued by the law, and more specifically to those of prevention and deterrence. These objectives form part of the refinement of civil liability. For present purposes, it is not a matter, however, of succumbing to a purely punitive logic: the measure pronounced ought ideally to benefit the animal concerned⁵¹ — which lends support to the idea of favouring the consecration of pure animal harm, rather than exploring the avenue of potential civil fines or hoping for the admission in French law of punitive damages. The recognition of pure animal harm would have the advantage, beyond its function of promoting the intrinsic value of the animal, of not relegating the cost of harm to the sole derivative harm dependent upon the animal's economic value. The problem is patent when one observes the significant variations of this patrimonial value, which undermines a protection that deserves to be harmonised.

17. Making responsible beyond the economic value of animals. In civil terms, the harm caused to an animal can be today both costly and derisory, which leaves one, in the latter case, dubious about the aptitude of civil liability to fulfil its normative function. It suffices to observe how the economic value of the animal constitutes a compensatory framework of variable geometry, necessarily weakening the effect of the measures hoped for at the conclusion of a liability action. The finding is easy to make — but also to deplore — in what it causes civil protection of the animal to mean: if harm is caused to a racehorse, the price of the fault (attached to the derivative harm of the owner) can be estimated in tens of thousands — or even hundreds of thousands — of euros; if harm is caused to a horse destined for slaughter, its value is fixed at approximately 750 euros; similarly, if harm is caused to an Ashera breed cat, the value at stake can be estimated in tens of thousands of euros; if harm is caused to a shelter dog, a goldfish, a common alley cat... their value approaches zero. Truly, “all animals are equal, but some are more equal than others”.⁵² What is to be concluded? In civil matters, a wrongful act causing harm to an animal, reduced to its patrimonial value alone, may very well cost the wrongdoer nothing at all; and this regardless of the gravity of the fault or of

⁵⁰Aulus Gellius, *Noctes Atticae*, bk. 20, ch. 1, Discussion between the jurist Sextus Caecilius and the philosopher Favorinus concerning the Law of the Twelve Tables. For the connection between this anecdote and the functions of civil liability, see S. Picasso, “L'introduction des dommages-intérêts punitifs en droit des contrats — Rapport argentin”, *RDC* 2010, no. RDCO2010-3-054, p. 1107. For a reading in criminal law, see B. Perrin, “Le caractère subjectif de la répression pénale dans les XII Tables”, *Revue historique de droit français et étranger* (1922-), Fourth Series, Vol. 28 (1951), pp. 383–405.

⁵¹In cases of the animal's death, see *infra*, no. 43.

⁵²G. Orwell, *Animal Farm*, original edn. 1949, Culturea, le patrimoine des lettres, 2022, p. 89.

the harm. Indeed, certain judgments explicitly attest to this variable geometry governing the consideration of the animal. Illustrative of this is a judgment in which a court of appeal, assessing the quantum of damages owed to an animal protection association that had intervened in a case of mistreatment inflicted on animals, held that:

"[I]t is above all appropriate to relativise the extent of the harm evoked by the civil party to the measure of the objective consequences suffered by the animals and to recall in particular, under the head of non-pecuniary harm, that while animals are unquestionably sentient beings deserving of care and attention commensurate with their living nature, it is necessary to maintain a requisite moderation in the assessment of harm arising from injuries that do not affect human beings."⁵³

In that case, the “requisite moderation in the assessment of harm arising from injuries that do not affect human beings” is founded on one knows not what principle (other than a supposed ontological hierarchy reflecting the judge's personal opinion). The argument nonetheless enabled the perpetrator of the mistreatment to be ordered to pay the association, under the head of non-pecuniary harm, the sum of 1 euro. Assuredly, the sum is, to say the least, “moderate”... By engaging in such reasoning, the judge, under the pretext of relativisation, explicitly imposes a minimisation of the condition of the mistreated animal, establishing an almost non-existent civil liability, and a correspondingly discounted protection. “How much more is a man than a sheep”,⁵⁴ St Matthew would confirm. From the standpoint of the functions of civil liability, at a time when the appropriateness of punitive damages is under discussion, or of reinforcing the judge's power to “aggravate” liability to combat lucrative faults (notably to better prevent harm caused to nature and to living beings), it is difficult to understand why the reparation of harm suffered by animals remains dogmatically relegated to the symbolic level. The normative function of civil liability must be restored in this area — for there is nothing to justify its failure to find expression here. A modernisation imperative thus emerges. In the light of these elements, the legal response to mistreatment inflicted on animals can no longer be left to the criminal sphere alone, whose objective of retributive justice must be complemented by that of corrective justice.

Is this not the stake of the modernisation of animal protection in France today, corresponding, in accordance with the Report accompanying loi no. 2021-1539 of 30 November 2021, both to moving beyond the repressive posture and to the promotion of the human-animal bond? The Senate and the rapporteurs of the recent Act of 30 November 2021 on strengthening the fight against animal cruelty have indeed recalled the necessity of advancing the objectives of protection “beyond the sole fight against cruelty” and of “modernising” the legislative framework.⁵⁵ To this end, the report displays the idea of moving beyond the sole “repressive posture” and of “promoting the bond between animals and humans”. While no clear account is given of what such a “bond” comprises,⁵⁶ can one not see therein an open invitation to civil law to play a more useful part in the protection of the animal? Indeed, the letter of the Civil Code has long remained frozen, imprisoned by a dogmatic

⁵³The passage is reproduced in Crim. 12 June 2019, no. 18-84.504, unreported (appealed decision: CA Nîmes, 19 June 2018).

⁵⁴Matthew 12:12.

⁵⁵Report no. 844 (2020–2021) of Mme Anne Chain-Larché, submitted on behalf of the Committee on Economic Affairs, filed 22 September 2021: <https://www.senat.fr/rap/120-844/120-844.html>.

⁵⁶For an analysis of this bond from the perspective of criminal law, see nonetheless P. Eric, “Réformer les relations entre les hommes et les animaux: fonction et usages de la loi Grammont en France (1850–1914)”, *Déviance et Société*, 2007/1 (Vol. 31), pp. 65–76.

heritage. The Code has, however, undergone important developments since 2015 through the simplification law modifying Book II, and through the 2016 Act relating to the reconquest of biodiversity enshrining pure ecological harm.⁵⁷ These developments have transformed the spirit of the Code, creating the conditions of possibility for exploiting the renewed potential of the law of liability.

2. The Possibility of Exploiting Civil Liability

18. The abandonment of the dogmatic heritage: *exit* the *bien par nature* (the property by nature). After centuries of naturalistic assignment maintaining the animal in the category of movable property, “practice does not yet appear to have seized upon Article 515-14 of the Civil Code and its potential”,⁵⁸ as Professor Fabien Marchadier notes. The spirit of civil law is deeply marked by a reifying imaginary.⁵⁹ That imaginary was formally brought to an end by the 2015 simplification law. While some repeat at will that this law has at best only a symbolic effect,⁶⁰ that is assuredly not the case, for at least two reasons. The first concerns the interpretation that may be given to the placement of Article 515-14. Indeed, the numbering follows on from the provisions relating to persons, but the text inaugurates Book II dedicated to property (*biens*).⁶¹ This materialises the animal's position between persons and things, which refers to its apprehension as an *interest* (etymologically *inter esse*: “situated between”) — which opens fundamental prospects for evolution in phase with the new stakes of civil liability.⁶² The second concerns the existence of a genuine upheaval, which might be described as historic, produced by the redrafting of Article 528, too often forgotten. The former Article 528 was a text of ontological blockage. It provided that:

"Movable by their nature are animals and bodies that can be transported from one place to another, whether they move themselves or can only change position by the effect of an external force."

The former Article 528 imposed a discordance between the normative definitions of the animal, scattered between the corpus inherited from the conceptions of 1804 and that of the Act of 10 July 1976 on the protection of nature, which is at the origin of Article L. 214-1 of the Rural and Maritime Fishing Code — which already described the animal as a “living being endowed with sentience”. The Civil Code instituted an insurmountable definition of animal nature, in conflict with the biological one provided for by the Rural Code. The Civil Code's prescription was indeed formidable in that the recourse to the pseudo-naturalist argument (the

⁵⁷Loi no. 2016-1087 of 8 August 2016.

⁵⁸*RSDA*, 1-2/2019, p. 23.

⁵⁹H. Kassoul, "Le bien par nature. Quand le Code civil imagine la nature animale", in *Nature de l'Homme, nature du droit. Les Rencontres de Thémis et Sophia* (2nd edn.), Proceedings of the conference of 4–5 November 2021, Poitiers, forthcoming in the journal *Lexsociété*.

⁶⁰See in particular M. Pirrotta and M.-C. Lasserre, "L'animal dans la procédure de divorce", *RSDA* 1/2022 – Conference Proceedings [First Part] "L'animal saisi par les procédures", 28 January 2022, Nice, H. Kassoul, M.-C. Lasserre, G. Leray (dir.), for whom "the scope of these provisions is primarily symbolic" and, borrowing an expression from Ph. Simler, are those of a provision with a "cosmetic" effect.

⁶¹On the "eminent position afforded" to Article 515-14, see: J. Leroy, J.-P. Marguénaud, "La migration de la sensibilité des animaux du Code rural au Code civil. Une révolution théorique 40 ans après la loi no. 76-629 du 10 juillet 1976", *Parlement[s], Revue d'histoire politique*, 2022/3 (no. HS 17), pp. 77–91.

⁶²See *infra*, nos. 20 and 24.

animal is by nature a *good/property*), conforming to the cosmology and to Christian precepts,⁶³ enclosed the living being in a reification of principle⁶⁴ and, above all, one that was irrefutable.⁶⁵ The being was a *bien* (property) by nature, and it was an animal by artifice — a perfect subversion of realities. The sentience referred to in the Rural Code was powerless to found, in civil law, reparation of harm caused to the animal other than through the medium of the owner's rights. Thus, under pre-2015 law, the ascendancy of property law prevailed, instituting a sophism: a *bien* (good/property) does not suffer; the animal being a *bien*, it does not suffer either. Consequently, the *bien par nature* of the Civil Code could not be recognised as having an interest, still less its own harm, since the *bien* cannot, by nature, be either interested or a victim.⁶⁶ It is on this point that the contribution of the 2015 Act is most significant: it reconciles the texts.

19. Reconciled texts. Since 18 February 2015, Article 528 of the Civil Code no longer refers to the movable “nature” of the animal.⁶⁷ The text has, moreover, been purely and simply purged of any allusion to the animal. The animal is now the subject of a single definition, of an exclusively biological character, carried by a new Article 515-14 that stands in perfect conjunction with Article L. 214-1 of the Rural Code. The former naturalist dogma of Article 528 has been abrogated and supplanted by the modern naturalism of scientific origin described in Article 515-14. This substitution operation has lifted the ontological obstacle that the Civil Code maintained against any idea of recognising a properly animal harm. The dissonance between the codes has accordingly ceased, revealing the animal's extraction from its patrimonial status.

One might then object that the new Article 515-14 provides that “subject to the laws protecting them, animals are subject to the regime of property”. Does this not undermine the value of the animal's redefinition? Assuredly not: this specification does not amount to maintaining the *statu quo ante*. The subjection of the animal to a regime is a legal technique distinct from the definition of its nature. The normative effect of the definition cannot be obscured, nor, by a regrettable shortcut, confused with that of the regime.⁶⁸ The fact is that to

⁶³The cultures and imaginaries underpinning the legal relationship between humans and animals, and its meanings, explain in part why the animal has never been recognised as a victim of harm inflicted upon it. Whereas the Book of Exodus prohibits the killing of another's animals, scholastic doctrine clarified its scope, explaining the exclusion of any interest proper to the animal in favour of an anthropocentric one: “He who kills an ox does not sin because he kills the ox, but because he harms another in his property.” The Bishop of Hippo writes that the principles prohibiting harm to others — such as “Thou shalt not kill” — do not apply to animals, which lack reason, which “prohibits any fellowship with us.” This logocentric reading persists to this day, although it has been extensively deconstructed, as has the dogma of the “proper to man”, notably by the anthropological, ethological, and biological sciences. See H. Kassoul, “Les fondements de l'éthique animale...”, *op. cit.*; “Le bien par nature...”, *op. cit.*

⁶⁴Saint Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, vol. 2, Le Cerf, Paris, 1997, II-II, q. 64: “He who kills another's ox sins, not because he kills that animal, but because he wrongs his neighbour in his property.”

⁶⁵Saint Augustine, *The Catholic and Manichaeic Ways of Life*, Works, “Christian Morality”, Paris, Desclée de Brouwer, 1949, II, XVII, 59; *The City of God*, I, 20, Works, Paris, Gallimard, 2000, vol. 2, p. 31. Add E. Baratay, “Le christianisme et l'animal, une histoire difficile”, *Ecozona, European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment*, 2011, 2(2), p. 125; by the same author, “Le christianisme et les animaux. De la dévalorisation à la prise en compte”, *Revue d'éthique et de théologie morale*, vol. 306, no. 2, 2020, pp. 37–49; R. Larue, *Le végétarisme et ses ennemis, vingt-cinq siècles de débats*, Paris, PUF, 2015, p. 98.

⁶⁶CA Bordeaux, 5e ch., 3 May 2004, RG no. 02/05504, JurisData no. 2004-271846.

⁶⁷Academic commentary also notes that the legislature took care to amend Articles 522, 564 and 2501 of the Civil Code so that they no longer imply that animals are movable or immovable property: J. Leroy, J.-P. Marguénaud, “La migration de la sensibilité des animaux du Code rural au Code civil...”, *op. cit.*, pp. 77–91.

⁶⁸See M. Pirrotta and M.-C. Lasserre, art. cit., for whom the definition is symbolic solely on the ground that it “is not intended to create a genuine legal regime for the animal”, adding further that “the opposition between persons and things appears as an ‘impassable distinction’ preventing any incursion into one or the other category; it is not one and the other, but rather one or

this sentient being, a regime is attached, because this is a necessity. The legislature has not, however, (yet) deemed it appropriate to create a *sui generis* regime. It therefore refers to the rules of the property regime, which are merely functional, without those rules defining the animal's essence. This is a regime substitute of which it should be underscored that it introduces a protective dimension through the reservation expressly foregrounded in the text — the essential consequence of which is that the property regime applies only to the extent necessary.⁶⁹

The objections having been set aside, it is now appropriate to draw the consequences of this new context and to bring to light the potentialities it generates for civil liability. To do so, it remains to demonstrate that the principles of civil liability are applicable to harm caused to an animal and that such harm can take on the character of recoverable damage, regarded as an infringement of an interest proper to the animal. Is it necessary, and is it possible, for this purpose, to consider the animal henceforth as an *autre* — an “other” within the meaning of civil law?

20. The application of the principles of civil liability: the animal as *autrui*? Having been freed from its dogmatism, the Civil Code can now permit a zoocentred taking into account of harm caused *to* the animal. The question remains whether the principles of civil liability allow the author of harm to be held liable to repair the damage caused to an animal. A reading of Article 1240 of the Civil Code reveals that it is the harm caused to “another” (*autrui*) for which the author must answer. This problem may be resolved by two distinct routes. The first consists in demonstrating that the animal is an *autrui* within the meaning of this provision. It remains the case, however, that this result encounters ideological resistance. The second rests on the idea that the existence of an *autrui* is not necessary for animal harm to be regarded as recoverable, notwithstanding the terms of Article 1240.

First, the animal is an *autrui*. In fact, the quality of being sentient is shared by the animal and the human person. Jean-Jacques Rousseau already affirmed this in his *Discourse on the Origin and Foundations of Inequality Among Men*: sentience is a quality “common to the beast and to man”.⁷⁰ Furthermore, the latter also answers perfectly to the definition of Article 515-14: the human being is a living being endowed with sentience, which makes it possible to mark the relationship of alterity and identity that exists between human and non-human animals. Thus, save for denying human nature, the consecration of Article 515-14 has the effect of elevating the animal to the status of an *autre*: the animal is another (than the human) living being endowed with sentience (like the human). It is certainly not another person, but it is indeed another sentient living being. Now, the harm caused to *autrui* obliges the one through

the other. In this respect, the pet remains (for the moment) assimilated to a somewhat atypical movable chattel, specifically protected, but a chattel nonetheless!". It is on the basis of this argument of assimilation — essentially doctrinal in nature — that the dogmatic binary vision persists of a Civil Code that has, however, entered a new era both in terms of its philosophy and the techniques it enables (see *infra*, esp. nos. 20 and 24).

⁶⁹For an example of reasoning distinguishing the fate of animals from that of other chattels in tenants' patrimony, see CA Poitiers, 22 Nov. 2018, 18/000842: "The eviction of animals from the rented premises is a mere consequence of the eviction of tenants and their property, but unlike the other property of the spouses Y..., wherever they are relocated, they will require appropriate care and maintenance to survive. The fact that they are ultimately intended, in whole or in part, for food does not detract from this necessity. From the documents produced to the court, it appears that small animals may be entrusted to the SPCA or to relatives, and nothing prevents animals normally kept in pasture from being entrusted to local farmers, and no genuine impossibility of proceeding in this manner has been seriously invoked."

⁷⁰Complete Works of J.-J. Rousseau, vol. 1, Furne, 1835, p. 534: "If I am obliged not to harm my fellow man, it is less because he is a rational being than because he is a sentient being; a quality (...) common to the beast and to man."

whose fault it occurred to repair it — and Article 1240 of the Civil Code does not provide a general clause of liability with respect to other human persons alone, but with respect to *autrui*.

Second, liability can exist without *autrui*. Article 1246 of the Civil Code, relating to ecological harm, is included within Sub-title II on “extra-contractual liability” and provides that “any person responsible for ecological harm is bound to repair it”. This provision may be regarded as removing the requirement of an *autrui* from the framework of liability. The wording of the text institutes a model of liability with no reference whatsoever to an *autre*, resting entirely on the foundation of harm, which makes it possible to underpin the idea that liability can be founded on purely animal harm. Furthermore, the Commissioner-General for Sustainable Development institutes a lexicon consistent with this idea when, under the head of reparation for interim losses, for example, it refers to an animal species as a “damaged entity”⁷¹ or “entity affected by the harm”.⁷²

In conclusion, nothing prevents the application of the principles of civil liability to harm caused to the animal from a zoocentred standpoint. It remains to verify whether there can exist recoverable damage — that is, an infringement of an interest proper to the animal.

21. The characterisation of harm: the animal as interested party. The rule has long been demonstrated in utilitarian ethics: if the animal is sentient, it can suffer; if it can suffer, it has an interest in not suffering;⁷³ whence there emerges a ground of “solidarity of interest [of man] with the organic world”.⁷⁴ The primary interest of the sentient being is therefore simply a negative interest that is detachable from a theory of rights and from any consideration relating to legal personality. It is, as such, a transpersonal interest. The demonstration is also legal, as shown by the work of Gérard Farjat on “centres of interests” (*centres d'intérêts*) dedicated to these “familiar entities” that constitute “points of legal imputation”.⁷⁵ If the granting of legal personality is a possibility that the legislature may seize to advance the animal's condition, its absence must not become an obstacle to such improvement: the non-personified animal is not, for that reason, without interests. The issue is moreover exacerbated when it is a question of

71 “Préjudice écologique, bien dimensionner la réparation des dommages”, in L. Monnoyer-Smith (dir.), *Théma. Essentiel*, Ministry for Ecological and Solidarity Transition, Dec. 2018: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/Th%C3%A9ma-%20Pr%C3%A9judice%20%C3%A9cologique.pdf>

72 “Comment réparer des dommages écologiques de moindre gravité?”, in *Théma. Analyse*, Ministry for Ecological and Solidarity Transition, May 2017: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/Thema%20-%20Comment%20reparer%20les%20dommages%20ecologiques%20de%20moindre%20gravite.pdf>

73 See P. Singer, *Animal Liberation*, Paris, Grasset, 1993, p. 39; J.-B. Jeangène Vilmer, “Le critère de la souffrance dans l'éthique animale anglo-saxonne”, in J.-L. Guichet (dir.), *Douleur animale, douleur humaine: données scientifiques, perspectives anthropologiques, questions éthiques*, Paris, Quae, 2010, pp. 191–199; *Éthique animale*, PUF, esp. pp. 104–122. The ingenuity of utilitarian ethics, in particular that of Peter Singer, lies precisely in demonstrating responsibility towards animals by positing an argumentative framework purged of rights theory. The strategy is effective in that it makes it possible to free oneself from the ideological or metaphysical debates that the question of rights provokes, often passionately but also in a sclerotic manner. Since the debate is divisive, it offers no prospect of political will asserting itself in a context not yet ready to accept the reform. Now, if responsibility is relegated to a criterion that is the object of a blockade and political circumlocutions, it follows the fate of that criterion: animal protection suffers both a form of abandonment and a failure at the normative level. The utilitarian method is therefore judicious in that it makes it possible to escape such a pattern by choosing the most constructive means of achieving the objective pursued. It thereby rests on an argumentative base that aims to be technical.

74 To borrow the terms of Hans Jonas in his ethics of responsibility, who nonetheless endeavours to demonstrate that the reduction of Man to a form of ontological isolation marks the “diminishment of his essence”. It follows that the struggle against the dehumanisation of Man implies that nature retains its own dignity, opposed to the arbitrariness of our power: H. Jonas, *The Imperative of Responsibility*, Champs Essai, Flammarion, 2009, p. 261 et seq.

75 G. Farjat, “Entre les personnes et les choses, les centres d'intérêts. Prolégomènes pour une recherche”, *RTD civ.* 2002, 221.

responding to harm caused to an animal without an owner, or harm caused *by* the owner — who in that case cannot be the victim of his own conduct.⁷⁶ Indeed, the interest of the victim currently envisaged (the owner) may be contradictory to that of the primary victim actually harmed (the animal).

It must be observed that the treatment of the animal in civil liability has not been updated: neither the subject matter nor the litigation has freed itself from the dogmatic framework of the former Article 528 of the Civil Code. They remain frozen, in a form of self-censorship, facing an equally frozen image of the animal as an object incapable without interests. This dissonance is no longer warranted and ultimately calls for an *aggiornamento* of the law of civil liability in which the animal is considered not as the object of harm but as a victim.

22. Treating the animal as a victim. At the purely lexical level, a careful examination of the texts and case law reveals that the animal is already commonly described as a “victim”. Article R. 322-123 of the Insurance Code thus refers to “animals that are victims of accidents and subject to slaughter”. Decree no. 2019-722 of 9 July 2019 on the compensation of damage caused to domestic livestock by wolves, bears, and lynxes contains an Article 2 that is literally applicable “in the event of damage caused to farm animals”. This text refers to “ovine or caprine victims”, “animal victims”, and “livestock herds that are victims of attack”. Section III provides that “the report referred to in Section II includes the identification numbers of the holding and of the animals that are victims of the damage”. In all of these cases, when the word “victim” is used, it does not refer to an owner — the owner of the injured animal or of the herd — but exclusively to the animals intrinsically targeted. Furthermore, interpreting Articles L. 411-1 and following of the Environmental Code, the Conseil d'État held that the object and scope of the aforementioned provisions is “to preserve the herds themselves, and not solely the patrimonial value they represent”.⁷⁷ The point is clear: the victim is preserved for its own sake, and the animal, by virtue of the laws protecting it, can therefore be a victim. The Criminal Chamber of the Cour de cassation also refers to the fate of “domestic animals that are victims of mistreatment”,⁷⁸ “victims of failure to care”.⁷⁹ Finally, “animal victims” are also explicitly assimilated to “human victims” in the circular concerning the discovery of envelopes, parcels, containers, and substances suspected of containing dangerous radiological, biological, or chemical agents.⁸⁰ The victimological terminology of animals, it can be seen, is already seized by the law. It should not be denied that this approach gives rise to difficulties.

⁷⁶See *infra*, no. 32.

⁷⁷CE, 6e–5e combined chambers, 18 Dec. 2019, no. 419898, unreported.

⁷⁸Crim. 12 June 2019, no. 18-84.504, unreported, *op. cit.* (“while it is certain that this accident gave rise to a degree of anxiety on the part of G. and F. M. regarding the fate of their animal, it is not established that they should be granted compensation in respect of non-pecuniary loss. This claim shall be rejected”). The courts of first instance had convicted the owners of the dog and ordered 1,000 euros as a civil fine, finding the action to be abusive. The appellate court did not find the proceedings abusive but held, however, that “in equity, there is no basis for applying Article 700 of the new Code of Civil Procedure.”

⁷⁹Crim. 24 June 1992, no. 92-80.123.

⁸⁰Circular no. 750/SGDSN/PSE/PPS of 18 Feb. 2011.

23. Difficulties. The animal cannot be a creditor.⁸¹ Its incapacity to invoke a right of claim — the very right that underpins the obligation between the author of harm and the one who sustains it — may appear aporetic. How, then, could the animal — possessed of interests but lacking legal personality — be a victim? To overcome this obstacle, one must carefully consider the place of the victim in civil liability since the new Article 1246 of the Civil Code on pure ecological harm. But let us first return to the definitions. The victim may be presented as “any person who suffers harm to their rights or interests”.⁸² Such a definition, however, is generally attached to criminal law.⁸³ The victim is therefore not conceived through the right of claim, but through the prism of the criminal offence. In parallel, in civil matters, the notion of victim is rather ghostly: it does not appear in the texts that found the right to compensation and yet it is tirelessly invoked as an indispensable protagonist in the liability framework. It is then represented only as a party to an obligational relationship. This is not the only possibility,⁸⁴ as a re-reading of the etymology of the word will attest. What is a victim?

24. Possibilities. Initially, *victima* derives from classical Latin and designates the “‘beast offered in sacrifice to the gods’ then ‘that which is sacrificed’, literally and figuratively”.⁸⁵ The word’s primary meaning is an exclusive reference to the animal — to the point that, historically, some were scandalised at the existence of “human victims”,⁸⁶ whereas the victim is by nature an animal. From the Latin *vinco, ere* (to conquer), the one who is *victus* is the one whose body is beaten. Under the form *vincio, ire* (to bind), the victim is the bound being, the prisoner: such is the condition of the animal led to the altar. The *victimaire* (*victimarius*) moreover designates the minister of the sacrificial altar, or the merchant of animals destined for it, just as the *victimator* is the one who strikes the beast. It is plausibly only from the seventeenth century onwards that, by extension, the victim came to be understood as a human person who suffers from the wrongdoing of others,⁸⁷ to the point of eclipsing the ancient meaning of the term. The evolution of the word in its usage thus attests to a semantic subversion of which the law has retained only the most recent effects. The idea persists nonetheless of a being taken as a scapegoat, as Professor Hervé Piant recalls: “the victim, like the sacrificial animal, is, fundamentally, innocent and suffering”.⁸⁸ The victim is thus determined by its passivity. Echoing the Latin, Gérard Cornu defines the victim as the one who,

81On the exclusion of the classifications of responsible party, debtor, creditor, and debtor, see M. Lacroix and G. Gidrol-Mistral, “L’animal: un nouveau centaure dans les curies de la responsabilité civile?”, *Revue du notariat*, 120(2) (Chambre des notaires du Québec).

82V° “Victime”, in S. Guinchard and Th. Debard (dir.), *Lexique des termes juridiques*, Dalloz, 30th edn., 2022 [criminal law/criminal procedure]. Add: v° “Victime”, in A. Bénabent and Y. Gaudemet, *Dictionnaire juridique*, LGDJ, 2nd edn., 2022: “a person sustaining harm (physical, moral, or material)”.

83No entry for “Victim” is provided in the *Lexique des termes juridiques* under “civil law”.

84See, for instance: L. Neyret, *Atteintes au vivant et responsabilité civile*, thesis pref. C. Thibierge (dir.), LGDJ, Bibl. de droit privé, vol. 468, 2006, nos. 641 et seq.: “The broadening of the notion of victim beyond persons alone, by admitting a depersonalised victim, is made possible thanks, on the one hand, to the etymological and philosophical potential of the notion of ‘victim’ and, on the other hand, to several legal arguments favourable to the objectivisation of the notion of victim.” The author proposes recognising the “living” as a “victim in fact” (*ibid.*, nos. 644 and 645).

85V° “Victime”, in A. Rey (dir.), *Dictionnaire historique de la langue française*, Le Robert, 2022, electronic version.

86For an example, see V° “Victime”, in *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 13, Pom-Regg / by a society of men of letters; arranged and published by D. Diderot, 1751–1765, pp. 240 et seq.

87See H. Piant, “Victime, partie civile ou accusateur? Quelques réflexions sur la notion de victime, particulièrement dans la justice d’Ancien Régime”, in B. Garnot (dir.), *Les victimes, des oubliées de l’histoire?*, Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2000.

88H. Piant, “Victime, partie civile ou accusateur?...”, art. cit.

personally sustaining harm, stands in opposition to the one who causes it.⁸⁹ So conceived, the victim is defined by antagonism: it is not the author of the harm. It “sustains”, passively, and is distinguished thereby from the one who generates the harm, who is active. Must the passive protagonist hold rights in order to be recognised as a victim? Since the doctrinal definition refers to harm that is “personal”, one is tempted to answer in the affirmative. One might also resist this temptation. The legislature does not attach such a criterion to the victim; indeed, it does not define the victim at all. It can even dispense with it: the new Article 1246 of the Civil Code, providing that “any person responsible for ecological harm is bound to repair it”, makes no reference — not even implicitly — to the existence of a victim. In recognising the recoverability of environmental harm, does the text consecrate a harm without victim? That would perhaps be too expedient an admission. Indeed, like the other foundational rules, it makes no mention of a victim.

Yet, as had already been sensed, it is the harm that determines the prescriptive framework of liability, and not the victim. The latter plays only the role of an embodying figure, of explanatory value. If there is, however, a lesson to be drawn, it lies in the revolution of the obligational relationship born of liability for pure ecological harm: Article 1246 of the Civil Code demonstrates that there exist harms without creditor-victims. The victim, as the sole seat of an infringement, is therefore sometimes distinguished from the creditor of the obligation. It is the entity — personified or not — that sustains the harm. From this it follows that the recognition of a proper harm is not dependent upon the capacity of the victim itself to be bound by an obligation. The existence of a purely animal harm therefore presupposes neither legal personality nor patrimony.

Ultimately, the recognition of pure animal harm is possible at the substantive level, provided that the potential of the subject — renewed since 2015 — is exploited. At the procedural level, this recognition rests on the identification of claimants capable of defending an interest that is not their own. In this utilitarian logic — that is, a logic structured by a theory of interests rather than rights⁹⁰ — the notion of claimant then becomes an essential pivot in the implementation of liability. Civil procedure is, in this respect, a law that is itself structuring of other areas of law. If no substantive reform of liability or of the legal status of the animal is necessary to admit pure animal harm, the liability action that would permit compensation for this head may perfectly well be adapted.

II. THE POSSIBLE ADAPTATION OF LIABILITY ACTIONS

25. A refocused action, calibrated measures. The limitations of the actions currently employed have demonstrated their inadequacy for the protection of the animal's own interests. The renewal of the spirit, as well as the provisions, of the Civil Code has demonstrated that the potential of civil liability has been left unexploited by reason of the inhibition of judicial practices incapable of being generalised or systematised. These practices can already evolve towards the recognition of purely animal harm that can be compensated through the simple adaptation of the liability action. The choice of action is determinative in restoring the animal's

⁸⁹V° "Victime", in G. Cornu (dir.), *Vocabulaire juridique*, 14th edn., 2022, PUF, Quadrige.

⁹⁰This is precisely the advantage of utilitarian theory: it avoids the debate on the categorisation of beings and things and does not require the creation of legal personality. See H. Kassoul, "Les fondements de l'éthique animale", art. cit., no. 38. The utilitarian arguments must therefore not be conflated with the question of animal rights (see *supra*, no. 4).

own interest to the centre of attention (A), and thereby allowing the pronouncement of measures calibrated to that interest (B).

A. AN ACTION REFOCUSSED ON THE ANIMAL'S OWN INTEREST

26. Procedural repercussions. Since the animal is recognised as a sentient being, its status as a victim has been demonstrated, and the existence of pure animal harm is conceivable at the substantive level, it follows that, at the procedural level, its own interest in having the harm it sustains taken into account should be capable of being defended. Is it possible to envisage a legal action whose object would be to defend this own interest? Is this possibility already actualisable *de lege lata* or does it presuppose legislative reforms *de lege ferenda*? In other words, the question arises as to whether the substantive renewal previously brought to light is compatible with the existing law of civil procedure. To this end, it seems opportune to favour positions that do not imply upheavals — that is, to prefer re-readings, capable of being conducted by the judge, to re-writings.

27. Options available. Following the celebrated proposal of Gérard Cornu and Jean Foyer,⁹¹ a distinction is drawn between two categories of actions: ordinary actions (*actions banales*) and designated actions (*actions attitrées*). Ordinary actions are open to any interested party provided that they invoke a direct, vested, current, and legitimate interest in bringing proceedings. Designated actions, for their part, are open to certain categories of persons determined by law to defend legally determined interests. It is readily understood that the recognition of an ordinary action for reparation of pure animal harm would be inopportune, running up against serious obstacles (1). Conversely, this would not be the case for a designated action, which would prove on the contrary promising — perfectly suited to the objective pursued and without disrupting the legal order (2).

1. The Inopportune Ordinary Action

28. The hypothesis of an ordinary action and the prerequisite of animal legal personality. In the usual representation of civil liability, the action is ordinary: the victim alleging to have sustained harm brings proceedings in order to obtain reparation of its damage. This vision has something hegemonic about it. The idea is still widespread that “the claimant in a liability action is accordingly the injured party; any injured party, but only an injured party”.⁹² Within this framework, the victim must demonstrate that it holds a personal interest — that is to say, an admissible interest. This action allows the victim to ask the court to realise a pre-existing substantive right, namely the right to reparation. The civil liability action is accordingly apprehended as the accessory of a subjective right to reparation; it gives rise to

⁹¹G. Cornu and J. Foyer, *Procédure civile*, PUF, Thémis, 1996, p. 335.

⁹²H., L. and J. Mazeaud and A. Tunc, *Traité théorique et pratique de la responsabilité civile délictuelle et contractuelle*, vol. 2, 6th edn., 1970, Montchrestien, no. 1866, cited by L. Raschel, *Le droit processuel de la responsabilité civile*, thesis pref. L. Cadet (dir.), 2010, vol. 25, no. 31.

subjective litigation: the admissibility of the action resides in the invocability of this right to reparation, and its merits depend upon the existence of that right.⁹³

Now, no such ordinary civil liability action exists for the benefit of the animal. Such an action would presuppose that the animal itself holds the action and can invoke a right to reparation in its favour — both of these requirements presupposing its legal personality, which is precisely what we seek to circumvent by situating ourselves within a theory of interests.⁹⁴ This does not, however, preclude envisaging the hypothesis of a legal reform recognising such personality. Academic commentary tends to consider that nothing opposes the recognition of a technical legal personality for the animal, when it is in the animal's interest,⁹⁵ a “hemiplegic” personality conferring upon it the status of creditor but not that of debtor.⁹⁶ But this seems capable of being achieved in France only at the price of a systemic reform — both procedural and substantive.

29. The extent of a systemic reform. Several rules of civil law and civil procedure would need to be adapted to ensure the representation of the animal party, the legal framework currently being designed only for natural and legal persons. A few illustrations will suffice to demonstrate the extent of the reform required.

First, it will be necessary to determine who holds the power to represent the animal and the modalities for attributing that power. If one instinctively thinks of the owner, would it not also be necessary to provide for the modalities of attribution of the power of representation for unowned animals, or in the event of a conflict of interests between the animal and its owner? Will it be necessary to have recourse to the court to appoint a provisional administrator? Will the law need to designate a “substitute guardian”? How will competition between the different representatives of the animal be regulated?

Second, at the procedural level, when one person represents another in proceedings, the rule *nemo alieno nomine lege agere potest* (no one may litigate in another's name) requires that the procedural documents include the identity and contact details of the person represented.⁹⁷ A claim brought by the animal would therefore need either to be subject to a derogatory procedural regime or to include such information, which would imply the construction of a formal “identity” for the animal.

Furthermore, the reparatory measure would be made for the benefit of the animal, which would accordingly need to be endowed with patrimony to receive the indemnity. The modalities of administration of this patrimony would therefore need to be defined — modalities that cannot simply transpose those currently provided for protected adults or legal persons. Although this patrimony would have only limited utility, being designed to receive active elements (the animal not being capable of being a debtor of obligations) in certain circumstances (in the event of harm caused to a surviving animal or, conceivably, in the case

⁹³See however L. Raschel, *Le droit processuel de la responsabilité civile*, thesis pref. L. Cadet (dir.), 2010, vol. 25, no. 28.

⁹⁴See *supra*, no. 21 and *infra*, no. 30.

⁹⁵J.-P. Marguénaud, "L'animal sujet de droit ou la modernité d'une vieille idée de René Demogue", *RTD civ.* 2021, p. 591; J.-P. Marguénaud, F. Burgat and J. Leroy, "La personnalité animale", *D.* 2020, 28.

⁹⁶F. Marchadier, "Le préjudice subi par l'animal", *op. cit.*, esp. p. 32.

⁹⁷N. Fricero, *Procédure civile*, Lextenso, Mémentos Gualino, 19th edn., 2022, no. 48.

of a liberality consented for its benefit), it is nonetheless a whole theory of animal patrimony that would need to be developed.

Finally, the idea that the animal's legal personality should be instituted only in its interest — meaning that it would cease as soon as the animal could find itself in the position of a debtor — would disturb many procedural provisions. For example, when a party loses its case, it may, depending on the circumstances, find itself the debtor of certain sums: the costs, an indemnity for non-recoverable expenses, damages for abuse of the right to bring proceedings, a civil fine... But what is to be decided when the animal loses its case? Would it be necessary to neutralise these essential procedural provisions (at the risk of breaking the equality between litigants according to whether they are opposed to a natural or legal person on the one hand, or to an animal person on the other), or to shift their burden onto the animal's "representative"? Would it be necessary here too to provide a particular rule in the Code of Civil Procedure to organise this transfer? One might object that it is not necessary to provide for everything and that case law will be able to interpret the texts so as to adapt them "to the extent necessary" to the problems of animal legal personality. But this is to forget that in civil procedure, the imperatives of legal certainty are predominant and that vagueness harms the proper administration of justice.

It can thus be glimpsed that the introduction of animal legal personality would generate a quantity of adaptations whose technical implications do not permit immediate solutions to be hoped for. This is why one must not place all hope in a systemic reform that currently encounters both uncertainties and debates about the proportionality between the means advocated and the objectives pursued; all the more so since systemic reform in procedural matters requires taking into account all the interests of litigants. Portalis made the principle of proportionality a cardinal aspect of legislation: "the solicitude of the legislature is obliged to be proportionate to the multiplicity and importance of the objects upon which it must rule".⁹⁸ Those who favour the consecration of animal legal personality nonetheless pursue a legitimate objective of "effectively strengthening [protection] at the civil level".⁹⁹ Yet this objective, which must be pursued, appears capable of being achieved other than through such a systemic reform consecrating animal legal personality. It may be observed, moreover, that the reparation of pure ecological harm was not accompanied by a personification of nature.

2. The Promising Designated Action

30. The absence of the prerequisite of animal legal personality. Ordinary actions are not the alpha and omega of the theory of action. Alongside them stand the so-called designated actions, which rest on the attribution, by a rule of law, to a person of an authorisation to act — that is, *locus standi*. This is what follows from Article 31 of the Code of Civil Procedure, which specifies that certain persons may be authorised to act "to raise or challenge a claim, or to defend a determined interest".¹⁰⁰ Designated actions are a remarkably flexible instrument since they allow, as the case may be, the exercise of the action to be restricted to certain categories of persons — beyond the existence of a personal interest — or, on the contrary, a "displacement

⁹⁸Portalis, "Discours préliminaire sur le projet de Code civil", in *Discours, rapports et travaux inédits sur le Code civil*, 1844, Joubert, p. 7.

⁹⁹J.-P. Marguénaud, F. Burgat and J. Leroy, "La personnalité animale", *D.* 2020, 28.

¹⁰⁰CPC, Art. 31.

of the circle of persons admitted to act”¹⁰¹ by conferring upon a person the authorisation to defend an interest other than its own.¹⁰² This “determined interest” can be that of a collectivity¹⁰³ (the action of associations in defence of the collective interest¹⁰⁴), the interest of another person (these are substitution actions: for example, the *ut singuli* action by which a member of a company brings proceedings against the manager for reparation of harm caused to the company itself,¹⁰⁵ or again the action brought by the liquidator of a debtor in judicial liquidation, who defends the collective interest of creditors, an action that one author has demonstrated does not rest on a mechanism of representation but indeed on substitution to the debtor¹⁰⁶), but also a non-personified interest!

This last situation can be illustrated by several examples: consider the action for reparation of pure ecological harm by which associations are authorised to defend the interest of nature,¹⁰⁷ or the class actions by which an association is authorised, at least in the first phase of the action, to defend the interest of the members of a group of indeterminate individuals who are victims of the same failure attributable to a professional.¹⁰⁸ These are original actions that are not substitution actions, given the absence of a substituted party endowed with legal personality.¹⁰⁹ But if the concept of these actions doubtless remains to be invented, they

101N. Hoffschir, "Étude: l'action en justice", in E. Vergès (dir.), *Procédure civile*, Lexbase [online], 2022, no. 4-1-1.

102F. Kernaleguen, "Intérêt, qualité, pouvoir: le ménage à trois de la théorie de l'action?", in *Justices et droit du procès: du légalisme procédural à l'humanisme processuel. Mélanges en l'honneur de Serge Guinchard*, Dalloz, 2010, pp. 771–782, esp. p. 773.

103I. Omarjee and L. Spinoli, *Les actions en justice au-delà de l'intérêt personnel*, Dalloz, Thèmes & Commentaires, 2014.

104A strict reading of Article 31 as cited implies that it is the "law" that is the source of such authorisation. Yet in the judgment of 18 September 2008 cited above (*supra*, no. 11), the Cour de cassation clearly states that the association's standing is recognised "even in the absence of legislative authorisation". This leads certain authors to consider that there is here "an entirely pretorial authorisation of the Cour de cassation" (C. Chainais, F. Ferrand, L. Mayer and S. Guinchard, *Procédure civile*, Précis Dalloz, 36th edn., 2022, no. 220), a "general pretorial authorisation" (*ibid.*, no. 215), and others to express the idea that "the defence of collective interests by an association has fallen within the domain of ordinary actions", signifying thereby that, for an association, defending the collective interest falling within its objects is equivalent to defending its own interests (N. Fricero, *Procédure civile*, Lextenso, mémentos Gualino, 19th edn., 2022, no. 42).

105C. com., Art. L. 223-22, al. 3.

106B. Ferrari, *Le dessaisissement du débiteur en liquidation judiciaire. Contribution à l'étude de la situation du débiteur sous procédure collective*, thesis pref. P.-M. Le Corre (dir.), 2021, Lextenso, Bibl. du droit des entreprises en difficulté, nos. 235 et seq.

107C. civ., Art. 1248.

108C. consom., Arts. L. 623-1 et seq.; Loi no. 2016-1547, 18 Nov. 2016, de modernisation de la justice du XXI^e siècle, Arts. 60 et seq. (Loi no. 2008-496, 27 May 2008, portant diverses dispositions d'adaptation au droit communautaire dans le domaine de la lutte contre les discriminations, Art. 10; C. trav., Arts. L. 1134-6 et seq.; C. envir., Art. L. 142-3-1; Loi no. 78-17 of 6 January 1978, Art. 37; CSP, Arts. L. 1143-1 et seq.).

109A substitution action is characterised "when a person — the substitute — acts to defend the interests of another — the substituted — without it being possible to consider there to be any representation" (J. Théron, "Ordre et désordre dans la notion de partie", *RTD civ.* 2014, 231). For one author, the substitution action bifurcates in the sense that the substitute holds an autonomous action enabling him to exercise the substituted party's action (E. Jeuland, "Quelques questions sur l'action de substitution 'à la française'", in *Justices et droit du procès: du légalisme procédural à l'humanisme processuel. Mélanges en l'honneur de Serge Guinchard*, Dalloz, 2010, pp. 749 et seq., esp. p. 752). He envisages extending these actions to the defence of the environment, which nonetheless appears to presuppose the legal personality of environmental elements (E. Jeuland, art. cit., p. 758). The concept of substitution action is therefore not employed in relation to the animal, since the idea of substitution suggests the replacement of one person by another, even though the author discusses substitution actions independently of the substituted party's legal personality (E. Jeuland, *Droit processuel général*, op. cit., no. 63). As regards the class action, certain authors see therein a substitution action in the first phase: E. Jeuland, "Retour sur la qualification de l'action de groupe à la lumière de la loi de modernisation de la justice du XXI^e siècle", *JCP G* 2017, doct. 354; C. Boillot, "Action de groupe et règlement amiable", *JCP G* 2017, doct. 155, esp. no. 9. But such is not the case if one adopts a conception of the substitution action as presupposing the legal personality of the substituted party. Comp., demonstrating that it is rather a "new" and "sui generis" action irreducible to a substitution action given the necessity that the group be constituted for the judgment to produce

nonetheless exist and are perfectly compatible with Article 31 of the CPC, which refers to actions designed for the defence of “determined interests” that do not presuppose the incarnation of those interests in a legal person.

In these various situations, the party that acts represents nobody: it is recognised as holding both the standing and the exercise of a personal legal action to defend interests that are not its own. To use the terminology of certain authors, these are “claims brought by persons who cannot be the recipients of the rule of law”.¹¹⁰ It would therefore be perfectly conceivable to recognise such a designated action in defence of the animal's interest. This action could be centred on the animal's own interest — the animal being the sole recipient of the rule of law as victim of the harm — without necessitating the granting of legal personality to the animal, given the total absence of any representation. The characterisation proposed by Gérard Farjat of “centre of interests” (*centre d'intérêts*)¹¹¹ to characterise the animal resurfaces here to reveal its full pertinence.

In contrast to the systemic reform required by the recognition of an ordinary action, the conditions for instituting a designated action prove accessible. Only the person who acts in defence of the animal's interest will have the status of a party, and only that person will hold the creditor status in relation to the ordered compensation (or the debtor status in relation to sums owed in the course of the proceedings). No sum will need to appear in the animal's “patrimony”, even if it will be necessary to ensure that the result of the action genuinely benefits the latter.¹¹²

In so doing, the designated action opens advantageous prospects, well-suited to the objectives pursued by the action. This may be appreciated by attempting to identify the conditions for the admission of the action and its potentialities.

31. The *de lege lata* admission of the owner's authorisation. Standing to act presupposes a legal authorisation pursuant to Article 31 of the CPC. Ideally, the legislature should therefore intervene to specify the holders of the action, as it did for pure ecological harm. However, it is not certain that a legislative intervention is indispensable. One may ask whether the owner is not already authorised to defend the own interest of his animal *de lege lata*. Two arguments may be invoked in support of this hypothesis.

First, a normative argument: case law has already itself caused an authorisation to emerge.¹¹³ This has occurred in favour of associations for the defence of collective interests falling within their objects.¹¹⁴ From a normative standpoint, there is nothing perplexing about adopting an open reading of the “law” referred to in Article 31 of the CPC, in keeping with the

substantive effects: v° “Action de groupe”, *Rép. proc. civ.*, B. Allard and J. Jourdan-Marques, Dalloz, 2021, no. 213. In our view, the absence of determination of the group's members in the first phase of the action precludes the idea of substitution — for want of personification and hence of replacement of one person by another — but nonetheless characterises an action in a “determined interest” of the same order as that which could be exercised in relation to the animal.

110J. Héron, Th. Le Bars and K. Salhi, *Droit judiciaire privé*, Lextenso, 2019, nos. 76 et seq.

111G. Farjat, “Entre les personnes et les choses, les centres d'intérêts: Prolégomènes pour une recherche”, *RTD civ.* 2002, 221.

112See *infra*, nos. 36 et seq.

113N. Hoffschir, study cit.: “The legislature, and even the judge, sometimes authorise a person to act in defence of an interest that is not their own.”

114See *supra*, no. 11.

idea now accepted that the case law of the Cour de cassation constitutes a “norm”.¹¹⁵ The judge thus appears capable of revealing, at the very least, an authorisation not expressly formulated by the statute but implicitly carried by it.

A substantive argument, second: one may think that, in the same way as the pursuit of statutory objects by an association implicitly authorises it to defend the collective interests encompassed therein, ownership also naturally carries an authorising function. The owner holds strong prerogatives for defending his property, including through legal proceedings — whether real or personal. The actions available by virtue of the right of ownership are not exhaustively enumerated. Now, when the “property” (*bien*) is a sentient being endowed with its own interest, the authorisation derived from the right of ownership to defend the “property” ought to extend to the protection of the sentient being's own interest, which must include the exercise of actions for compensation of harm. Furthermore, the evolution of property law tends increasingly to demonstrate that this right carries a “social function”, as Jossier had foreseen.¹¹⁶ In other words, ownership imposes duties. The authorisation of the owner would in substance be merely the reflection of the duty incumbent upon him to provide the necessary care to his animal and to ensure its welfare.¹¹⁷ So envisaged, ownership — in that it is not merely a right but also a source of duties — is not a poor ally in the quest for better civil protection of the animal.¹¹⁸ Moreover, the pursuit by the owner of his own interests constitutes a driver for the compensation of animal harm, insofar as the claim brought under this head will very often be the accessory of the claim for compensation of harm sustained by the owner.

Beyond the normative role that the judge can immediately assume, if one wished to enshrine these principles in legislative text — which could be a sound approach for prompting change — a provision could specify that “the owner of an animal may act to obtain compensation for harm of which that animal is a victim”. This provision could take the form of a statute (for example, a second paragraph added to Article 515-14 of the Civil Code) or indeed of a decree (it would be possible to rehabilitate Chapter I of Title II of Book III of the Code of Civil Procedure, left vacant by the disappearance of possessory actions, to introduce this rule in Article 1264 within the chapter renamed “Actions in Defence of the Own Interest of an Animal”).

32. The *de lege lata* admission of a subsidiary authorisation for associations. It remains to envisage the subsidiary situations in which the animal has no owner or is in conflict of interests with its owner, in particular in cases where the owner is the author of the harm. An

¹¹⁵Ass. plén., 2 Apr. 2021, no. 19-18.814.

¹¹⁶*De l'esprit des droits et de leur relativité. Théorie dite de l'abus des droits*, Dalloz, coll. "Bibliothèque Dalloz", reissued 2006 from the 2nd edn. of 1939, esp. nos. 254 and 305.

¹¹⁷In her doctoral thesis, Maud Cintrat notes that the animal's nature is a source of constraint on property rights. She writes that: "in sum, respect for the animal's sentience is incumbent upon the person who has custody of and responsibility for it. One may infer from this that the animal's essence limits the prerogatives the owner holds over the animal and gives rise to genuine individual protection of the animal's health" (M. Cintrat, *Recherche sur le traitement juridique de la santé de l'animal d'élevage*, thesis Aix-en-Provence, V. Michel and G. Nicolas (dir.), 2017, no. 79). It seems that one may therefore sustain here that the norms derived from this constraint can be at once the creators of duties and of auxiliary powers — that is, of powers enabling those duties to be fulfilled.

¹¹⁸It may also be noted that, since the animal is, subject to reservations, governed by the regime of movable property, ownership may be acquired by simple possession provided that the legal conditions are met.

association should then be able to act in the animal's own interest (and not in the collective interest).¹¹⁹

This situation appears to be already addressed by Article 2-13 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, which authorises certain associations or foundations to exercise the rights of the civil party in respect of certain offences committed to the detriment of animals.¹²⁰ This authorisation to exercise the rights of the "civil party" should in logic be confined to the intervention of associations before criminal courts¹²¹ and not concern the civil courts, even though the Cour de cassation has had occasion to interpret analogous provisions more broadly by admitting that associations so authorised may seise the civil courts.¹²²

Admittedly, as regards the scope of the authorisation, one cannot deny that Articles 2-1 and following of the Code of Criminal Procedure were conceived with reference to the collective interest¹²³ and not the interests of individual animals. But the aforementioned Article 2-13 does not expressly provide for such a limitation to the collective interest. One may therefore argue for an interpretation of that provision which permits the defence of the animal's own interest to be integrated therein, provided that this falls within the objects of the authorised association. In the light of the renewal of the underlying stakes, case law could admit that the obligation of the responsible party to answer for pure animal harm implies that, where no action is brought by an owner, the authorised association or foundation may claim, within the framework of its civil action, compensation for that harm. This interpretation would prove opportune for ensuring the effective protection of the animal against its owner and for avoiding the pitfalls of compensating harm to the collective interests of associations.¹²⁴ This reasoning is all the more justified in situations in which the animal is placed in the care of the association.

As regards the tethering of such an action to the prosecution of criminal offences, this appears legitimate. The action of associations and foundations is necessarily subsidiary in relation to that of the owner, somewhat in the manner of the action reserved for controllers in insolvency proceedings. This subsidiarity justifies imposing an additional condition on the exercise of the action, presupposing the existence of animal mistreatment without an owner capable of defending it. Furthermore, since what is at stake is the animal's harm, it is appropriate to limit the concurrence of actions, which is achieved by concentrating civil parties within the criminal proceedings.

¹¹⁹On this question, see *supra*, no. 11.

¹²⁰CPP, Art. 2-13: "Any association that has been regularly declared for at least five years at the date of the acts and whose statutory objects include the defence and protection of animals may exercise the rights recognised to the civil party in respect of the offences provided for by the Criminal Code and by Articles L. 215-11 and L. 215-13 of the Rural and Maritime Fishing Code repressing the abandonment, serious or sexual abuse, acts of cruelty, and mistreatment of animals, as well as intentional harm to the life of an animal. Any public interest foundation may exercise the rights recognised to the civil party under the same conditions and with the same reservations as the association referred to in this article."

¹²¹V° "Action civile – Demandeurs à l'action civile", *Rép. dr. pén. proc. pén.*, C. Ambroise-Castérot, Dalloz, 2017 [updated: 2020], no. 458.

¹²²With regard to Article L. 142-2 of the Environmental Code, it is considered that an association authorised to exercise the rights of the "civil party" could act "in reparation both before the criminal judge and the civil judge, in respect of acts causing direct or indirect harm to the collective interests which they have as their object to defend and constituting an offence against the legislative provisions relating to the protection of nature and the environment and against the texts adopted for their application". See Civ. 3e, 30 Nov. 2022, no. 21-16.404. See also, for hunting associations and federations: Civ. 2e, 7 Dec. 2006, no. 05-20.297; Civ. 2e, 14 June 2007, no. 06-15.352.

¹²³V° "Action civile – Demandeurs à l'action civile", C. Ambroise-Castérot, *op. cit.*, no. 422.

¹²⁴See in particular L. Neyret, *Atteintes au vivant et responsabilité civile*, thesis pref. C. Thibierge (dir.), LGDJ, Bibl. de droit privé, vol. 468, 2006, no. 668.

33. Engaging objective litigation. Once the owner is recognised as holding a designated action in defence of the animal's own interest, an objective conception of the dispute is deployed. The action does not reduce to the realisation of a substantive right held by a person. The objectivisation of litigation is not an abnormal situation in civil procedure — whether one thinks of insolvency proceedings or, closer to the situation under study, the action for reparation of pure ecological harm.¹²⁵ This configuration of proceedings, which “directly implements the rule of objective law”,¹²⁶ illustrates the autonomy of the action with respect to substantive law. As Motulsky writes, in objective litigation, “the subjective right constituted by the action does not, in this domain, have the character of an envelope beneath which lies buried a second subjective right — the one which, by its very nature, the action would aim to protect”.¹²⁷

Traditionally, however, there is a tendency to confine objective litigation to claims directed abstractly at compliance with legality in the general interest. Motulsky thus excludes the idea of objective litigation wherever the legal effect of the invoked rule “tends towards a performance”, limiting the category to actions aimed at “obtaining an objective judicial finding”.¹²⁸ It is not, however, useless to recall, conversely, that Duguit (placed by Motulsky among the “ultra-objectivists”¹²⁹), the pioneer of the notion of objective litigation, maintained that the law of civil liability fell wholly within the domain of “objective litigation”, seeing therein above all litigation designed to determine “whether the rule of law has or has not been violated by an act”.¹³⁰ For Duguit, the judge who orders reparation following the finding of a violation of the law “exercises objective jurisdiction” because “it is the condemnation judgment alone that conditions the birth of the claim”,¹³¹ attributing to Pothier the “error” of having considered that the debt arose from the delict.¹³² Today, the idea that a substantive right to reparation exists at the date of the harm — which the judge then realises — has prevailed,¹³³ but it is not without criticism, so artificial is it.¹³⁴ In any event, once the framework of civil liability can be purged of a creditor-victim, it is logical to reconnect with the Duguist perspective of objective liability litigation, which has nothing heterodox about it and which places the birth of the claim for the benefit of the claimant at the date of the judgment.¹³⁵ In this regard, it is fair to affirm that “objective litigation is no longer the pure proceeding

125M. Mekki, conference, in B. Parance and J. Rochfeld (dir.), *Faut-il modifier l'appréhension de la victime (et de l'intérêt à agir) à l'aune de la consécration du préjudice écologique?*, Cycle de conférences de la Cour de cassation: “Les grandes notions de la responsabilité civile à l'aune des mutations environnementales”, 20 June 2022, 37'35”, URL: https://youtu.be/0_kpbMH4HWI (accessed 23 Dec. 2022).

126H. Croze and C. Morel, *Procédure civile*, PUF, Droit fondamental, 1988, no. 152.

127H. Motulsky, *op. cit.*, no. 35.

128Ibid., no. 36.

129Ibid., no. 36.

130L. Duguit, *Traité de droit constitutionnel*, de Boccard, vol. 2, 3rd edn., 1928, § 31, p. 357.

131Ibid., p. 365.

132Ibid.

133See in particular on the question: P. Jourdain, “La date de naissance de la créance d'indemnisation”, *LPA* 9 Nov. 2004, no. PA200422407, p. 49. See e.g. in the context of insolvency proceedings, to determine whether the claim arose before or after the opening judgment: Com., 2 Nov. 2016, no. 14-24.540.

134P.-E. Audit, *La “naissance” des créances. Approche critique du conceptualisme juridique*, thesis pref. D. Mazeaud (dir.), Nouvelle Bibliothèque des thèses, Dalloz, 2015, esp. concl. no. 98.

135See thus: E. Jeuland, *Droit processuel général*, LGDJ, Domat droit privé, 5th edn., Dec. 2022, no. 286. The author does not, however, characterise liability litigation as objective, adopting a restrictive approach to that notion (ibid., no. 299).

traditionally brought against [an] act”.¹³⁶ It encompasses actions dedicated to the protection of non-personified interests. Such litigation is objective in the same way as the harm it aims to compensate.¹³⁷

An essential consequence of this characterisation as objective litigation lies in the fact that the “reparatory” measures can be conceived more broadly by the judge, who is not bound by the limits that the framework of the realisation of a pre-existing substantive right to reparation would impose upon him: he is here rather the architect — doubtless less constrained — of measures ensuring a compensation calibrated to the animal's own interest.

B. MEASURES CALIBRATED TO THE ANIMAL'S OWN INTEREST

34. Abandoning symbolism. One may wager that the measures for compensating pure animal harm will be modest. They might even confine themselves to symbolic damages, the judge being sovereign in his assessment. In other words, the recognition of pure animal harm does not in itself guarantee that the relativisation of harm caused to animals will not be replicated. Academic commentary already attests to the diversity of assessments by judges — most often without reasons — with regard to the evaluation of pure ecological harm: while a Pau magistrate was able to allocate €150 for the capture of a protected bird in 2003, he was equally able to grant a symbolic one euro for the death of a bird of prey in 2005, as did a judge in Aix for the elimination of a wolf that same year.¹³⁸ As for the Cour de cassation, applying the principles in force prior to the entry into force of the regime for reparation of pure ecological harm, it approved trial judges for having awarded a sum of €4,547 to the Sepanso federation “under the head of “environmental” harm resulting from the direct harm caused by the offence to the aquatic and marshy habitat”, without explaining how that amount had been calculated.¹³⁹ Recently, the Calanques National Park took issue with the Aix-en-Provence Court of Appeal for having limited the compensation for its ecological harm and used a calculation method that “corresponded to a purely mathematical and intellectual construction bearing no relation to the facts at issue”.¹⁴⁰ The Cour de cassation specified in its dismissal judgment that “the court of appeal, bound to ensure the full reparation of the ecological harm whose existence it had found, merely exercised its sovereign power to assess the method it deemed most appropriate for evaluating the indemnity suited to its reparation”. Ultimately, the judge may exercise his sovereign power to assess both the measures appropriate to the compensation of the harm and the instruments for measuring the alleged harm. It will therefore be necessary first to define more precisely the object, and then the modalities of implementation, of the compensatory measures (1). The measures ordered by the judge can only be ordered in the light of the harm: upon its assessment depends the evaluation of the damages. That assessment is mistakenly regarded as impracticable, on account of the animal's incapacity to testify to its suffering. It is nonetheless possible to measure the harm (2).

¹³⁶L. Cadiet, J. Normand and S. Amrani-Mekki, *Théorie générale du procès*, PUF, Thémis Droit, 3rd edn., 2020, no. 209, p. 296.

¹³⁷On the notion of objective harm: L. Neyret, *Atteintes au vivant et responsabilité civile*, op. cit., nos. 479 et seq., and more specifically 598 et seq. and 610 et seq.

¹³⁸V° “Responsabilité civile environnementale”, *Rép. dr. civ.*, M. Hautereau-Boutonnet, Dalloz, 2019, no. 266.

¹³⁹Crim. 28 May 2019, no. 18-83.290.

¹⁴⁰Crim., 4 Oct. 2022, no. 21-85.290.

1. Compensatory Measures

35. From reparation to compensation. The uncertainty surrounding the assessment of purely animal harm does not facilitate the determination of the conditions for its possible “reparation”. Emerging from the foregoing reflections is the technical deepening of the normative function of liability. It is indeed sensed that the measures ordered by the judge (or agreed between the parties within the framework of an amicable settlement) would be less measures of reparation *stricto sensu* than compensatory measures that may present a more loosened connection with the harm sustained. In other words, the measures would have less as their object the achievement of a “restoration to the original position”, a *restitutio in integrum*, than the compensation of the harm in another manner, more indirectly, within the framework of a broadly understood theory of reparation.¹⁴¹ Such an approach is permitted, from a procedural standpoint, by the objective nature of the litigation under consideration,¹⁴² which does not realise a pre-existing right to reparation. It will be indispensable to clarify further the insufficiencies of the strictly understood theory of reparation, before envisaging the openings permitted by recourse to the idea of compensation. If the restrictive theory of the reparation of harm proves ill-suited to pure animal harm, it is because neither reparation by equivalent — requiring the victim to be endowed with patrimony — nor reparation in kind — poorly suited to a harm of an extra-patrimonial nature — offers satisfactory prospects.

First, the question of the limits of reparation by equivalent arises. When damages are ordered as reparation by equivalent, they are intended to achieve that reparation *ipso facto* and subsequently fall under the free use of the victim. This situation cannot be transposed to the case of the animal, which cannot itself make use of the sums. The animal having no patrimony, it cannot benefit from a patrimonial gain capable of achieving a reparation by equivalent. To recall: the theory of interests adopted, implemented through a designated action, does not imply that the animal-victim be regarded as a creditor: it is the claimant who is the creditor of the damages. Would reparation in kind then be better suited to the individual interest of the animal?

Second, reparation in kind also encounters an obstacle. It accords poorly with extra-patrimonial harm, such as the *pretium doloris*, on account of the necessary “objective coherence” that must characterise the relationship between the harm repaired and the measure of reparation,¹⁴³ no measure being capable of objectively attenuating suffering. Moreover, as in the reparation of any bodily harm, reparation in kind poses a difficulty because, at the time when the question of liability is at stake, the victim of the harm has already received care. The time of the action and the time of the reparation are generally poorly matched: the civil reparation intervenes after the administration of care.¹⁴⁴ This is why the question seems exclusively compensatory, without allowing, as is the case for pure ecological harm, for the

141G. Wester, *Les principes de la réparation confrontés au dommage corporel*, thesis Univ. Lyon 3, dactyl., S. Porchy-Simon (dir.), 2021, no. 383: “legal reparation does not aim to cause the harm to disappear but to compensate the recoverable damage resulting from it. Reparation in kind allows the complete erasure of the harm only by way of exception.”

142See *supra*, no. 33.

143G. Wester, *op. cit.*, nos. 378 and 413.

144A comparable observation is made with respect to pure ecological harm, for which it is considered that “temporality in the context of environmental damage is, moreover, a disruptive element in reparation”, in A. Mure, *op. cit.*, no. 79. Cf. Ph. Brun, “Temporalité et préjudices liés au dommage environnemental”, in L. Neyret and G.J. Martin (dir.), *Nomenclature des préjudices environnementaux*, LGDJ, 2012, p. 182 et seq.

principle of reparation in kind to be posited.¹⁴⁵ These observations compel the conclusion that the reparatory logic of civil liability is not truly capable of responding to the objective pursued by the recognition of pure animal harm. It would, however, be possible to recommend compensatory measures that would nonetheless constitute measures in kind.

36. Compensating in kind? In her thesis, Guillemette Wester brings to light certain existing condemnations which appear, on the surface, to constitute reparation by equivalent, but which must nonetheless be classified as performance in kind. This hypothesis concerns condemnations to the direct financing of services designed to procure for the victim a compensatory advantage for the harm sustained, without “any sum of money transiting through its patrimony”.¹⁴⁶ It is in this sense that the aforementioned thesis refers to a category of measures designed for “reparation in kind by equivalent”.¹⁴⁷ Such measures correspond to the idea of compensation: the victim benefits from an advantage in kind financed by the responsible party, an advantage that is not objectively designed to cause the harm to disappear. This method is opportune and proportionate to the legal treatment of pure animal harm, principally for two reasons.

First — and this is essential — the measure, being “in kind”, does not have recourse to the victim's patrimony. The animal having an interest but lacking legal personality, a measure that makes it possible to dispense with transit through a patrimony is accordingly welcome.

Second, the measure in kind imposes an allocation of the sums awarded. This is a distinguishing feature between what is ordered by equivalent — leaving freedom in the use of the damages — and what is ordered for the purpose of procuring an advantage in kind — that advantage determining the use to which the damages must be put. Now, the allocation of the sums is indispensable in the case of harm to the animal, since the response to that harm must be confined to its individual interest and not to that of the owner.¹⁴⁸ The allocation thereby guarantees that the sums awarded benefit exclusively the interested party — that is, the non-creditor victim.¹⁴⁹

It is in this sense that the civil law responses calibrated to the animal's own interest will consist of measures in kind whose function is compensatory. These must be understood as those which, not transiting through the victim's patrimony, permit the payment of sums of money allocated to the financing of services benefiting the animal exclusively. The animal thereby benefits from advantages in kind through the awarded sums. This reasoning is operative *de lege lata* and presents itself as a tailored and immediate response. It remains, however, to define the modalities for implementing such measures, which rest on the principle of the allocation of the service.

¹⁴⁵The comparison with pure ecological harm also shows that the idea of reparation is globally rendered possible by the fact that the environment is envisaged as a whole that can be repaired asynchronously. The animal is not individualised but attached to the entity formed by its habitat, which must be restored in accordance with its reference *statu quo ante*. The benefit will accrue to the same broadly understood centre of interests — that is, to the habitat serving the damaged fauna, which may no longer be constituted of the same individual animals. The habitat is restored for the benefit of other animals that will come to inhabit it. Now, harm to an individual animal does not follow the same fiction.

¹⁴⁶G. Wester, *op. cit.*, no. 372.

¹⁴⁷G. Wester, *op. cit.*, no. 372.

¹⁴⁸The same necessity appears with regard to pure ecological harm: V. Rebeyrol, “Où est la réparation du préjudice écologique”, *D.* 2010, 1804.

¹⁴⁹See *supra*, no. 24.

37. The modalities of allocation. The principal concern surrounding the implementation of measures in kind is its allocation. How to guarantee that the sums awarded are allocated to the financing of an advantage benefiting the animal concerned? To recall: in the event of the success of the liability action, it is the claimant who will be the creditor of the damages, in the same manner as under the regime of Articles 1246 and following of the Civil Code relating to pure ecological harm. Now, since the claimant is not the victim, it must not be able to obtain for itself a non-compensatory service for the harm. However, the regime of the aforementioned articles does not provide for the modalities of allocation, merely positing the principle. Certainly, failure to comply with the allocation would constitute non-performance of the judicial decision, with the consequences thereby invocable,¹⁵⁰ but it is still necessary that such non-performance be established. This practical question appears determinative of the utility of the measure centred on a non-personified interest.¹⁵¹ This is why the imprecision of the modalities of allocation may be experienced as an obstacle. Proposals may already be formulated.

Several options¹⁵² are then possible, concerning either, on the one hand, the choice of an appropriate payment instrument or, on the other hand, recourse to the mechanism of consignment.

38. An allocated payment instrument. The practical issue arises from the fact that the payment of sums of money facilitates their free use for the payment of any service. In the present case, the sum of money, paid under the head of an allocated compensation, appears to

¹⁵⁰The creditor's failure to respect the allocation of the damages could have several consequences. First, it is likely that the debtor holds an action for restitution, reflecting the frustration of the *res judicata* authority of the condemnation judgment. Generally speaking, it is accepted that "the authority of *res judicata* cannot be raised where subsequent events have modified the situation previously recognised in proceedings". Now, events subsequent to the judgment may deprive compensation of its basis and bring about the neutralisation of *res judicata*. This has been held, for example, with regard to a judgment that awarded, to the lessee of a terminated commercial lease, "reinstatement allowances, for commercial disturbance and removal costs" which proved unfounded by reason of the tenants' failure to re-establish themselves. The action for restitution brought by the former lessor is then held admissible (Civ. 3e, 28 Mar. 2019, no. 17-17.501, P). Furthermore, academic commentary admits such a restitution action in the event of non-compliance with the allocation of damages awarded for reparation of pure ecological harm (G. Viney, P. Jourdain and S. Carval, *Traité de droit civil. Les régimes spéciaux et l'assurance de responsabilité*, Traités LGDJ, 4th edn., 2017, no. 227). Such actions are common in construction law in cases of allocated damages (Civ. 3e, 17 Dec. 2003, no. 02-19.034; Civ. 3e, 4 May 2016, no. 14-19.804, Bull. civ. III, no. 126). By analogy, one might consider that the failure to comply with the allocation of damages to the animal, if proved, opens an action for restitution in favour of the condemned party. Second, failure to comply with the terms of a judgment is assuredly a fault engaging the liability of its author. In matters of environmental harm, the aforementioned authors envisage that this liability may give rise to reparation in kind allowing the judge to order the restoration of the environment by a third party at the expense of the beneficiary (ibid.). This idea seems difficult to transpose to the indemnity allocated to the animal, insofar as the debtor has no interest in seeking such a form of reparation and the owner, authorised to defend the animal's interest but not benefiting from the compensation, will not act against himself for failure to respect the allocation...

¹⁵¹It must not be allowed for the recognition of pure animal harm to create an opportunist springboard for the owner seeking personal enrichment from the harm caused to his animal.

¹⁵²Recourse to a mandatary or an *ad hoc* administrator is excluded from this analysis, in keeping with the theory of interests defended — which does not rest on the management of a victim's patrimony. Furthermore, only the judge's perspective is considered, the parties being entirely free to negotiate contractually the modalities for establishing the allocation. This could indeed constitute a situation in which a bifurcation of the proceedings would be opportune, the judge ruling on liability and allowing the parties time to negotiate the modalities of the allocation without being divested, subject to the obligation to approve the agreement reached or to determine those modalities himself in the event of the failure of negotiations. Cf. in matters of pure environmental harm: M. Hautereau-Boutonnet, "Le contrat de réparation et prévention du dommage environnemental", *Énergie – Environnement – Infrastructures*, April 2019, étude 8; E. Truilhé and M. Hautereau-Boutonnet (dir.), *Le procès environnemental. Du procès sur l'environnement au procès pour l'environnement*, rapport GIP Justice, May 2019, p. 286 et seq.

require that allocation be ensured by a body controlling expenditure. This option does not have the virtue of simplicity and does not conform to the idea of an action without representation that has been advanced. Recourse to a cashless payment instrument might instead be envisaged. This idea is not new, in that it takes up the technique of the token, which locks the uses made of the means of payment and renders its holder captive of a closed market. If this works wonders in the market of arcade games or casinos, it also enables, for example, an employer to cover the meals of its employees by means of meal vouchers rather than lunch bonuses, or holiday vouchers and gift vouchers in lieu of various bonuses such as a Christmas bonus. It also justifies — to come closer to the animal context — animal protection associations offering sterilisation assistance in the form of “vouchers” intended for payment to the veterinarian. Whether one considers vouchers, cheques, or tokens, the essential idea remains that the payment instrument, being neither refundable nor exchangeable, ensures the allocation of its amount to the payment of certain pre-determined services. In the hypothesis of a condemnation to compensate purely animal harm, the debtor could therefore be condemned to finance such payment instruments — that is, vouchers dedicated to veterinary services, animal care, hygiene, and food (such vouchers are already offered by various major retailers) — which the creditor can choose in accordance with the allocation. They would present a double advantage.

The first advantage is that the sole use of this instrument suffices to guarantee the allocation, without the intervention of a guarantor third party or a mandatary charged with administering the sums.

The second advantage is that, while combating the possible opportunism of the creditor, it maintains a form of discretion and freedom in the use of the vouchers. The opportunism could occur at two levels: in terms of diversion of expenditure and in terms of the animal's lifespan. The diversion of expenditure calls for no particular comment, since it is simply avoided by the specialised payment instrument. By contrast, the question of the effects of the animal's death must be envisaged. It has arisen in the context of the *fiducie* (trust-like arrangement), a vehicle used in favour of an animal that survives its owner. If the animal's death releases the allocation and permits the transfer of funds to the patrimony of the animal's owner, such a release creates a conflict between the animal's interest and that of its owner. The latter could effectively hope for — or even cause — the animal's death in order to benefit from the effects of the extinction of the *fiducie*. Similarly, if sums of money were to be paid subject to an allocation that would end upon the animal's death, the same conflict of interests would undermine the viability of the mechanism. Specialised vouchers or cheques do not pose such a problem. In the event of the animal's death, they would not thereby enrich the owner.¹⁵³

It would still remain to determine by what means recourse to an appropriate payment instrument could be put in place.

First, can the judge directly order payment by means of this instrument? Nothing appears to oppose this. Indeed, the process of realising the law by the judge, as modelled by Motulsky and developed by the Caen school, implies a phase of concretisation of the law comprising a “concrete arrangement”,¹⁵⁴ which appears to leave the judge a degree of latitude, not being in principle limited in the choice of “concrete measures, taken from the array that the general and abstract legal effect of the rule of law [offers] him”.¹⁵⁵ Here again, just as the judge

153See *infra*, no. 43.

154C. Bléry, *L'efficacité substantielle des jugements civils*, thesis J. Héron (dir.), Bibl. dr. privé, LGDJ, 2000, vol. 328, pref. P. Mayer, esp. no. 104.

155C. Bléry, *op. cit.*, no. 119.

can assume a normative role in the interpretation of civil liability texts, he must not self-censor by neglecting all the possibilities offered by the richness of his office. Similarly, the defendant should be able to request that the condemnation be ordered in this form.

Second, if the judge does not order payment in this form, the question arises of the vocation of civil enforcement proceedings to intervene to compel the allocation. Now, insofar as the choice of enforcement measures belongs to the creditor, this is not the case. From a prospective standpoint, however, the development of digital civil enforcement proceedings could permit recourse to smart contracts capable of fulfilling an allocation function, which would nonetheless necessitate limiting the choices currently offered to the creditor for enforcement (requiring the establishment of special enforcement procedures for allocated indemnities).

It must be observed that, even if recourse to an allocated instrument is technically operative, the economic model underpinning this proposal has not yet been deployed, insofar as it would be necessary to designate the service providers that can usefully be solicited and that are capable of responding to the objectives pursued. Both their identification and the modalities for their participation in a mechanism designed to contribute to the realisation of a judicial decision call for practical solutions that remain to be devised for the proper administration of the measures. This is why, in the meantime, the technique of consignment deserves consideration.

39. The technique of consignment. Consignment consists of “a deposit of money, securities, or objects in the hands of a third party, on condition that it remit them to whoever is entitled”.¹⁵⁶ The practice is common in the law of sale and in construction law. In these contexts, however, it does not have a liberatory function. This function nonetheless underpins, as Professor Antoine Touzain recalls, a historical purpose of the technique.¹⁵⁷ Indeed, liberatory consignment has been neglected, not to say forgotten, even though it is a mechanism concurrent with payment and capable of satisfactorily extinguishing the obligation whose performance requires, for the creditor, compliance with certain obligations.¹⁵⁸ Applied to the use of damages, consignment could thus be rehabilitated as a mode of extinction concurrent with payment, since it would make it possible to guarantee the allocation of the sum owed by the responsible party. Conventional consignment thereby reveals, in this sense, its full potential so that third-party depositaries may be designated to convert the sums and restore them in the form of allocated vouchers or cheques.¹⁵⁹ For this purpose, it would be appropriate to explore the hitherto neglected role of the notary in the implementation of animal protection. It is, however, within the framework of an amicable resolution of the dispute that this avenue merits particular attention. Otherwise, judicial consignment could be used as a reimbursement fund upon presentation of invoices. Article L. 518-17 of the Monetary and Financial Code provides that “the Caisse des dépôts et consignations is charged with receiving consignations of any nature, in cash or in financial securities, provided for by a legislative or regulatory provision or ordered either by a judicial decision or an administrative decision”. The advantage classically recalled of recourse to the Caisse des dépôts et consignations is that its service is remunerated by the interest produced by the consigned sums. This is why the management carried out by the Caisse

¹⁵⁶V° "Consignment", in S. Guinchard and Th. Debard (dir.), *Lexique des termes juridiques*, Dalloz, 30th edn., 2022.

¹⁵⁷A. Touzain, *La consignation*, thesis dactyl., Paris II Panthéon-Assas, C. Brenner (dir.), 2018, no. 19.

¹⁵⁸A. Touzain, *op. cit.*, no. 1302: consignment rests on an escrow arrangement coupled with an allocation.

¹⁵⁹See *supra*, no. 38 (on recourse to non-fungible means of payment).

is free of charge. Furthermore, deconsignation may be effected both by post and digitally, by sending supporting documents. The mechanism fits within the habitual practices of this financial body, as well as within its public interest missions. The technique of consignation therefore appears a promising avenue, insofar as it appears operative under existing law. It thus remains for litigants and judges to avail themselves of this possibility in order that the feasibility of allocated compensation be demonstrated.

It finally remains to turn attention to the assessment of the harm.

2. The Measure of Harm

40. How to evaluate? At this stage, one argument directed against the thesis of pure animal harm is always feared, as invoked by certain town veterinarians: how is one to evaluate the animal's suffering, given the diversity of species and their resistance to pain? The question is interesting and ultimately reflects an erroneous belief that the evaluation of human *pretium doloris* does not already raise comparable questions! The diversity of sensitivities, personal histories, and the subjectivity of victims already place the expert in the role of a casuistic evaluator. The argument does not hold, and for this reason it is necessary for the practitioner to be sensitised to compensation law. Some will further object that it is not possible to evaluate the pain of beings not endowed with language. In that case, it is often the jurist who must open himself to the sciences. Let us recall that the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) has underlined that “the inability to communicate verbally does not mean that an individual does not experience pain and does not require pain-relieving treatment”.¹⁶⁰ This incapacity should even ground a reinforced consideration towards those who suffer from it, as expressed in Émile Zola's confession regarding his love for animals: “I believe indeed that my charity towards animals is made of the fact that they cannot speak, explain their needs, indicate their ills”.¹⁶¹

Not only, first, does the constraint of language exist and is it surmounted with respect to humans, but, second, it is also surmounted with respect to animals.

41. From the evaluation of harm in non-communicating humans... The victims of harm that are young children or certain categories of persons suffering from disability are not always able to express the level and nature of the suffering endured. INRA nonetheless recalls that numerous recent studies use validated measuring instruments and establish in particular “that intellectually disabled persons manifest specific reactions in response to painful phenomena caused by their condition, even if they have greater difficulty in localising pain or respond to it more slowly”.¹⁶² This is why for this category of persons, the evaluation of pain is more difficult, notably because of difficulties with verbal communication. However, “cross-assessments by those familiar with the patient and by unfamiliar observers provide good indications of the patient's state of pain and discomfort, provided that a validated tool is used”. For young children (aged 0-5), the evaluation rests on “the testimony of all interlocutors (...)

¹⁶⁰V° "Douleur", in *Terminologie de la douleur de l'IASP* (International Association for the Study of Pain).

¹⁶¹É. Zola, "L'amour des bêtes", in *Le Figaro*, 24 March 1896. Rue des Archives/Mondadori Portfolio/Rue des Arch.

¹⁶²P. Le Neindre (dir.), *Synthèse du rapport d'expertise réalisé par l'INRA à la demande du Ministère de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la Pêche et du Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche: "Douleurs animales: Les identifier, les comprendre, les limiter chez les animaux d'élevage"*, 2009, available at inrae.fr

and [endeavours] to identify the expressive patterns of discontent, emotional seeking, "physical pain" and psychological suffering".¹⁶³ It is useful to recall here that scientific interest, as well as ethical consideration, towards infants and disabled persons is recent. Indeed, as the INRA's collective expertise committee affirms, it was not until the late 1980s that the first articles dedicated to the pain of these patients emerged. A form of logocentric legacy long persisted, undermining the status of infants — and also of disabled persons — as moral patients, justifying, in particular, that infant surgeries be performed without anaesthesia.¹⁶⁴ The aforementioned report thus affirms that "it is very probable that nociception and pain in animals (if characterised as such) possess the same adaptive 'purposes', the same protective functions as in humans. Nociception and pain are just as vital for animals as they are essential to humans".¹⁶⁵

42. ...To the evaluation of harm in animals. Furthermore, INRA has studied the possible transposition of the conception of human pain to the animal, with reference to the definition adopted by the International Association for the Study of Pain. Indeed, this definition of pain — it being recalled that this notion is narrower than that of suffering (which includes psychic discomfort and stress) — may appear ill-suited. This is why INRA has adapted it specifically for animals: "pain is an aversive sensory and emotional experience represented by the animal's 'awareness' of the rupture or threatened rupture of the integrity of its tissues".¹⁶⁶ Beyond the adaptation of the definition, it is evident, for those willing to reason outside the law and set aside their assumptions about the work conducted with animals, that the conceptual approach is also operative, since the Institute uses it in reference frameworks already applied in the care given to animals and also in experimental protocols. Indeed, the evaluation of pain, and more broadly of suffering, in animals forms an integral part of animal experimentation projects founded on the use of identification and grading tools. Thus, from discomfort, to stress, to distress, the suffering caused to the animal can be assessed against indicators which the law can already seize. The Canadian Council on Animal Care (CCAC), based on definitions from the Federation of European Laboratory Animal Sciences Associations (FELASA), also proposes such indicators, which demonstrate that suffering can even be anticipated. A potential scale is used — which also makes it possible to classify invasive experiments and techniques according to the level of affliction. This scale also takes into account the adequacy of care provided to the animal, handling of the animal, and more generally practices likely to influence its welfare. These indicators constitute as many elements enabling the protocols to be refined, which routinely succeed in distinguishing the degrees of suffering endured but also the risks of suffering endured. In parallel, the protocols provide for levels of tolerance to suffering coupled with an "endpoint" — that is, the moment at which the pain or distress experienced by an experimental animal is brought to an end. In all cases, the evaluation can have recourse to physiological, behavioural, zootechnical (the performance of the farm animal, for example), parametric (relative to the normal behaviour of the species, such as level of activity, posture, weight, blood pressure, etc.) or non-parametric (presence or absence of certain indicators, such as vocalisation, lameness, closed eyelids, etc.) indicators. The foreseeable degree makes it possible to justify the appropriate analgesic protocol. Nomenclatures and grids exist and may

¹⁶³Report cited, p. 27.

¹⁶⁴H. Kassoul, "Les fondements de l'éthique animale. Révolutions et circonvolutions humaines autour de la sensibilité non humaine", *Université d'été de Poitiers 2019: Les animaux*, LGDJ, 2020, p. 29, esp. pp. 27 et seq.

¹⁶⁵Report cited, p. 33.

¹⁶⁶Report cited, p. 28.

consist, for example, of three levels ranging from mild pain (lameness, etc.) to severe pain (amputation, for example).¹⁶⁷ Specialists have recourse to species-specific dedicated scoring grids.¹⁶⁸ These levels are comparable to the reference frameworks currently used for human suffering and are therefore immediately mobilisable — and improvable as needed — by the experts who could be chosen by a judge, from the lists of judicial experts that would not only be veterinarians, but also specialists in animal husbandry, agri-food, aquaculture, wildlife, and other professionals best informed of the criteria for evaluating the condition of the animal concerned by the harm. It is nonetheless necessary to avoid believing that recourse to expert opinion is an obligatory passage. On the contrary, in a number of hypotheses, it can constitute a deterrent — both on account of its cost and its duration — that will discourage the claimant from formulating a claim for compensation of purely animal harm. While recourse to experts makes it possible to evaluate suffering, recourse to expert opinion as an investigative measure in proceedings is not necessarily useful. Expert knowledge could give rise to the development of nomenclatures enabling the judge and the parties to be guided in the evaluation of harm. These nomenclatures could indicate in simple terms the criteria enabling suffering to be located on a grading scale based on observable indicators or reference situations characterisable by a layperson. The evaluation of harm would thus be standardised for the benefit of a concern for procedural efficiency.

43. The case of the deceased animal. In light of the perspective that is ours — proposing an improvement of animal protection under existing law — it is not possible to envisage that purely animal harm could exist in the event of the animal's death. In the absence of the recognition of rights and patrimony attached to the animal, and in the logic of an action by authorisation founded on interest, the animal's death extinguishes the interest in bringing proceedings. If this solution is coherent at the technical level, it is nonetheless disappointing with regard to the normative function of civil liability in this area. How to accept that harm caused to the animal warrants compensation in civil law, but not its death? The fact is that the suffering of the deceased animal is no longer compensable for its own sake. Now, the principle of pure animal harm is to permit a compensation dedicated to the interest of the purely animal victim. One might nevertheless envisage having recourse to punitive damages or a civil fine, when the responsible party has caused the animal's death. It must also be noted that Article R. 655-1 of the Criminal Code is designed to sanction the most culpable acts, by providing that “the act, without necessity, publicly or otherwise, of voluntarily causing the death of a domestic, tamed, or captive animal is punishable by the fine provided for Class 5 misdemeanours”. The article is not concerned with suffering possibly caused to the animal, but with its unjustified elimination. It nonetheless enables, albeit perhaps too timidly, a sanctioning function to be fulfilled that civil liability cannot today satisfy.

¹⁶⁷See for ruminants: referring notably to the analgesic protocols according to pain intensity of Boreve (2010), M. Fauré *et al.*, "Douleurs animales. 2. Evaluation et traitement de la douleur chez les ruminants", *INRA Productions Animales*, Paris, 2015, 28(3), pp. 217–280. Add (for a multidimensional modelling of animal welfare): R. Botreau, *Évaluation multicritère du bien-être animal: exemple des vaches laitières en ferme*, thesis Institut des Sciences et Industries du Vivant et de l'Environnement (Agro Paris Tech), 2008.

¹⁶⁸For example, see the lameness scoring system for dairy cows: P.T. Thomsen, L. Munksgaard, F.A. Togersen, "Evaluation of a lameness scoring system for dairy cows", *Journal of Dairy Science*, 91(1), 2008, pp. 119–126; the pain assessment grid for horses: G. Bussièrès, C. Jacques, O. Lainay, G. Beauchamp, A. Leblond, J.L. Cadore, L.M. Desmaizières, S.G. Cuvellez, E. Troncy, "Development of a composite orthopaedic pain scale in horses", *Research in Veterinary Science*, 85(2), 2008, pp. 294–306.

44. Assessment. The absence of legal personality: such is the argument advanced by the few judicial decisions rejecting the claim for reparation of animal suffering. The animal is not a legal subject, write certain judges. Since the owner does not personally suffer from the harm to the animal, the *pretium doloris* cannot be compensated in favour of the owner, write others. Rather than seizing their normative function and judicial role, the courts cling to what could appear to be a reasoning error or a dogmatic posture. Indeed, it is postulated that the existence of the animal's harm is conditioned by the aforementioned arguments and, moreover, confined to the sole condition of the pet. This amounts, on the one hand, to abandoning the question to the legislature, and, on the other hand, to enclosing the measures calibrated to the animal within the sole question of its legal status.

We have sought to demonstrate that another route is possible *de lege lata*, without distinction between the animals' purposes, and that these arguments can be set aside by a careful reading of the texts of positive law. This route is limited, however, to the sole recognition of the *pretium doloris* as purely animal harm, resting on the rigorous and imaginative reception of the Act of 2015 modifying Book II of the Civil Code, and that of 2016 consecrating ecological harm.

Taking this step is therefore ambitious, commensurate with the stakes of protection and improvement of the human-animal bond defended by the legislature in the Act of 2021 on the fight against mistreatment.

Taking this step is also reasonable: it depends solely upon re-readings and not upon re-writings. In the objective approach to litigation, the choice of a theory of interest — supported by a procedural mechanism of authorisation rather than representation — opens the way to an *aggiornamento* in favour of the recognition of pure animal harm. The latter escapes the complexity of a multi-entry nomenclature, being concentrated on the sole *pretium doloris*. Its compensation depends on existing instruments such as compensatory measures in kind, which do not require transit through the victim's patrimony and permit the allocation of ordered services. The measures for realising the compensation may in turn have recourse to the technique of liberatory consignation. It is also already common to have recourse to expert knowledge to assess the condition and suffering of victims, including animals, as attested by the facts and procedure that led to the so-called “Saphir” judgment, but also by the in-depth work conducted in the animal sciences.

The *aggiornamento* of civil liability towards the recognition of pure animal harm therefore depends less on a new legislative intervention than on the disinhibition of courts that do not avail themselves of their power of interpretation and of the potential of civil liability; on this point, a “mental evolution of the judge”¹⁶⁹ may be hoped for. To encourage this, from the standpoint of the possible legal path, it remains to be hoped that the present contribution, sparing any legislative novelty, will encourage the formation of new jurisprudential choices.

A call to judges and litigants alike!

169J. Leroy, J.-P. Marguénaud, "La migration de la sensibilité des animaux du Code rural au Code civil. Une révolution théorique 40 ans après la loi no. 76-629 du 10 juillet 1976", *Parlement[s], Revue d'histoire politique*, 2022/3 (no. HS 17), pp. 77–91.

45. Annex: Summary Table of the Argument

TREATMENT OF THE ANIMAL	CHOICE OF ACTION	COMPENSATORY MEASURES	IMPLEMENTATION
THESIS DEFENDED			
Theory of interests Victim: <i>non-personified non-creditor</i>	Designated action Claimant: creditor Mechanism of authorisation	Compensatory measure Allocation Does not require transit through the victim's patrimony	<i>De lege lata De lege lata</i>
THESIS BYPASSED			
Theory of rights Victim: <i>personified creditor</i>	Ordinary action Claimant: non-creditor Mechanism of representation	Reparatory measure Requires transit through the victim's patrimony	<i>De lege ferenda De lege ferenda</i>

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